

Annual Report for Period:04/2004 - 03/2005

Submitted on: 06/22/2005

Principal Investigator: Warnick, Wendy K.

Award ID: 0101279

Organization: Arctic Research

Title:

Organizational Support to the U.S. Arctic Science Program

Project Participants

Senior Personnel

Name: Warnick, Wendy

Worked for more than 160 Hours: Yes

Contribution to Project:

Post-doc

Graduate Student

Undergraduate Student

Technician, Programmer

Other Participant

Research Experience for Undergraduates

Organizational Partners

Other Collaborators or Contacts

Activities and Findings

Journal Publications

Books or Other One-time Publications

Web/Internet Site

Other Specific Products

Contributions

Contributions within Discipline:

Contributions to Other Disciplines:

Contributions to Human Resource Development:

Contributions to Resources for Research and Education:

Contributions Beyond Science and Engineering:

Special Requirements

Special reporting requirements: None

Change in Objectives or Scope: None

Unobligated funds: less than 20 percent of current funds

Animal, Human Subjects, Biohazards: None

Categories for which nothing is reported:

Organizational Partners

Activities and Findings: Any Research and Education Activities

Activities and Findings: Any Findings

Activities and Findings: Any Training and Development

Activities and Findings: Any Outreach Activities

Any Journal

Any Book

Any Web/Internet Site

Any Product

Contributions: To Any within Discipline

Contributions: To Any Other Disciplines

Contributions: To Any Human Resource Development

Contributions: To Any Resources for Research and Education

Contributions: To Any Beyond Science and Engineering

**Arctic
Research
Consortium
of the
United States**

Member Institutions:

University of Alaska Anchorage

University of Alaska Fairbanks

University of Alaska Statewide

Alaska North Slope Borough
Dept. of Wildlife Management

Arizona State University

Bates College

Brown University

Center for Northern Studies

University of Colorado

Cold Regions Research and
Engineering Laboratory

University of Delaware

Dartmouth College

Desert Research Institute

Embry-Riddle
Aeronautical University

Foundation for Glacier
and Environmental Research

Idaho State University

Lamont-Doherty Earth Observatory
of Columbia University

Louisiana State University

Marine Biological Laboratory

Michigan State University

University of Massachusetts Amherst

University of Miami

University of New Hampshire

Northern Illinois University

Ohio State University

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Pennsylvania State University

San Diego State University

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21 June 2005

Simon Stephenson
Arctic Research Support and Logistics Program Manager
Office of Polar Programs, Room 755
National Science Foundation
4201 Wilson Blvd.
Arlington, VA 22230

Dear Mr. Stephenson:

Attached is one copy of the 4th Annual Report of the Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S. (ARCUS) as required in Section F-1 of Cooperative Agreement OPP-0101279, between the National Science Foundation and ARCUS. The report describes accomplishments for the period 1 April 2004 through 31 March 2005 and outlines projected activities for 1 April 2005 through 31 March 2006, the final year of this agreement.

Included in the annual report, as specified in the Cooperative Agreement, are:

- an executive summary outlining the major activities and accomplishments;
- a narrative summary of accomplishments, future plans, and discussion of major change in direction or pace, by individual task;
- a one-page summary showing costs by five major tasks: arctic community science planning, NSF Arctic Sciences Section coordination, arctic science education, information and outreach, and core support (Attachment A);
- a five-page, multi-column table, by individual activity, showing the currently approved five-year budget, the actual costs for years one through three, actual expenditures through March 2004 (year 4), the remaining funds or shortfall, and the proposed budget for April 2005-March 2006 (Attachment B);
- a one-page, multi-column table summarizing the entire cooperative agreement by Form 1030 categories, showing the currently approved five-year budget, the actual costs for years one through three, actual expenditures through March 2004, the remaining funds or shortfall, and the proposed budget for April 2005-March 2006 (Attachment C); and
- the proposed budget and the request for \$1,935,041.00 for the period of April 2005-March 2006 on NSF Form 1030 (Attachment D).

The ARCUS board of directors and staff are very pleased with the achievements of the past year and the work we have accomplished on behalf of the arctic research community and NSF. We look forward to continuing to work with NSF and the arctic research community on these important initiatives. If you have any questions, please feel free to contact me.

Sincerely,

Wendy K. Warnick
Executive Director

Fourth Annual Report Cooperative Agreement OPP-0101279 April 2004 through March 2005

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S. (ARCUS) has undertaken a variety of activities to enhance NSF arctic research programs through Cooperative Agreement OPP-0101279. ARCUS has worked with the scientific community to identify new research objectives, logistical requirements, and educational activities that benefit planning and implementation of NSF-supported science initiatives in the Arctic. Specific activities have been organized under four major tasks:

1. Arctic science planning—coordinating science planning for the arctic research community at several levels, including continuing examination of logistical requirements with the goal of improved access for all researchers in the Arctic;
2. Organizational support for the Office of Polar Programs Arctic Sciences Section programs, including the Arctic System Science Program and the Arctic Social Sciences Program;
3. Development and coordination of arctic science educational activities; and
4. Information and outreach activities disseminating timely information about arctic research to scientists, policy and decision-makers, and to the public.

An additional 5th “task” is the provision of core support for ARCUS’ NSF-funded activities—dedicated funding of the broad needs necessary to support this work regardless of the specific nature of activities from year-to-year.

1. ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING

Accomplishments under this major task include activities to address arctic research support and logistics needs, including:

- ∞ Ongoing distribution of the updated recommendations on research support and arctic logistics, providing long-term advice on arctic logistics and science support issues for the NSF Office of Polar Programs.
- ∞ Continuing development and maintenance of ALIAS, an arctic research support and logistics web site that serves as an information resource and access point for the research community.
- ∞ Working with the arctic research community, GIS experts, and NSF to provide community information resources to support research planning and analysis in the Arctic by using geospatial concepts and resources as a coordinating framework.
- ∞ Operating the project office and providing program coordination for the Study of Environmental Arctic Change (SEARCH) program.
- ∞ Supporting the development of a community science plan for the Bering Ecosystem Study (BEST), a research initiative proposed for the Bering Sea.
- ∞ Preparing a process to conduct a community survey to identify data coordination and data management needs for arctic research.

2. NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION

Accomplishments under this major task include a number of activities for the ARCSS Program and the Arctic Social Sciences Program, as well as the development of information and outreach materials on aspects of arctic research for the Arctic Section as a whole.

2.1 ARCTIC SECTION SCIENCE MATERIALS

Activities under this sub-task include:

- ∞ Coordinating community outreach and review for "Guidelines for Improved Cooperation between Arctic Researchers and Northern Communities."
- ∞ Developing and conducting an online survey to identify reasonable target dates, from the research community perspective, for Arctic Section proposals.

2.2 ARCTIC SYSTEM SCIENCE (ARCSS) PROGRAM COORDINATION

Activities under this sub-task include:

- ∞ Operating the ARCSS community science management office.
- ∞ Providing organizational support to the work of the ARCSS Committee (AC).
- ∞ Coordinating discussions, planning, and implementation for changes to the structure and process of ARCSS Program community science management.
- ∞ Coordinating the ARCSS-wide synthesis effort.
- ∞ Coordinating and supporting the work of the ARCSS data advisory working group.
- ∞ Coordinating and supporting a Human Dimensions of the Arctic System (HARC) science management office through a subcontract with the University of Alaska Fairbanks.

2.3 ARCTIC SOCIAL SCIENCES PROGRAM COORDINATION

Activities under this sub-task include:

- ∞ Planning and support for *Partnering with Arctic Communities*, which will be convened as a special session at the May 2004 Fifth International Congress of Arctic Social Sciences.
- ∞ Coordinating and supporting a community planning process to develop a social science research plan for the Bering Sea in order to establish responsible community-centered Bering Sea ecosystem research and partnerships between communities and researchers.

3. ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION

Activities under this major task include:

- ∞ Coordinating and managing the Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series to increase communication and collaborations among the dispersed arctic research community and arctic residents.
- ∞ Planning and implementing the second year of the Teachers & Researchers - Exploring and Collaborating (TREC) program, an educational research experience in which K-12 teachers participate in Arctic research as a pathway to improving science education through teachers' experiences in scientific inquiry.

4. INFORMATION AND OUTREACH

Accomplishments related to information distribution and outreach include:

- ∞ Publishing and distributing one issue of *Witness the Arctic* to over 10,000 subscribers.
- ∞ Developing and maintaining web-based resources for arctic research.
- ∞ Managing the Arctic Info listserve.
- ∞ Maintaining and expanding *The Directory of Arctic Researchers*.
- ∞ Convening the two-day *Arctic Forum*, a seminar highlighting important arctic research findings, in Arlington, VA in May 2004.

5. CORE SUPPORT

Accomplishments described in Core Support are direct project activities that benefit and support multiple NSF activities that cannot be identified with one specific project.

THE ARCTIC RESEARCH CONSORTIUM OF THE UNITED STATES
4th Annual Report

April 2004–March 2005
OPP-0101279

The narrative describes activity for the period April 2004 through March 2005, the fourth year of Cooperative Agreement OPP-0101279. Accomplishments and work in progress are described through March 2005, and projected activities are indicated for the period April 2005 through March 2006.

1. ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING

1.1 Arctic Research Support and Logistics

Accomplishments

- ∞ Continued distribution of the report, *Arctic Research Support and Logistics: Strategies and Recommendations for System-scale Studies in a Changing Environment*, published in October 2003.
- ∞ Distributed the report to individuals at all ARCUS-sponsored meetings and to several other arctic research meetings on request, including Arctic Science Summit Week 2004, the inaugural meeting of the Polar Research Board's Arctic Observing Network Panel, and the 2004 AAAS Arctic Science Conference.
- ∞ The report is also available as a PDF download on the ARCUS website.

Projected Activities

- ∞ Continue distribution of hard copies and availability of on-line edition.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None.

1.2. Logistics Internet Resources; Arctic Logistics Information and Support (ALIAS)

ALIAS is an Internet-based logistics support resource, designed and developed to serve as the primary access point and a comprehensive information source to help researchers to assess the feasibility of working in a specific area or on a specific research platform, plan the conduct of research, view current research and research support resources, and make useful scientific and logistics contacts in support of planned research efforts. Development of the ALIAS database and search and display tools has continued to increase the utility of ALIAS to the arctic research community and will continue for the next program year.

Accomplishments

- ∞ Added 19 vessel records to the database for a current total of 47. Vessel information includes ownership and management, physical characteristics (including performance capability), onboard scientific equipment and space, communications and data equipment available, and other vessel information.
- ∞ Added or revised descriptions of vessels and vessel scheduling to reflect information provided by vessel stakeholders.
- ∞ Continued adding data fields recommended by managers and users for vessel information and improving categorization and searchability with new structural fields in the database.

- ∞ Further expanded the use of CSS styles (style sheets) in the database to improve information display and the efficiency of data entry.
- ∞ Met with the ALIAS advisory group for guidance in expanding vessel data information and functionality. Worked with individual group members to provide specific input from each member's areas of vessel expertise. The advisory group is composed of representatives from the Forum of Arctic Research Operators (FARO) and the Arctic Ocean Sciences Board (AOSB) and represents a variety of international arctic research organizations:
 - *Martin Bergmann, Department of Fisheries and Oceans, Canada*
 - *Sara Bowden, Arctic Ocean Sciences Board (AOSB)*
 - *Dieter Fütterer, Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Sciences (AWI)*
 - *Anders Karlqvist, Swedish Polar Research Secretariat*
 - *Mike Prince, University-National Oceanographic Laboratory System (UNOLS)*
 - *Tom Pyle, Arctic Ocean Sciences Board (AOSB)*
 - *Odd Rogne, International Arctic Science Committee (IASC)*
 - *Simon Stephenson, Forum of Arctic Research Operators (FARO)*
- ∞ Presented the ALIAS project at the 2004 Arctic System Science Week in Reykjavik, Iceland, to increase international awareness of the project and improve project staff understanding of international context.
- ∞ Participated in the 2004 Fall meeting of the American Association for the Advancement of Science (AAAS), Arctic Division, and met with the directors of the Far Eastern Branch of the Russian Academy of Science (FEBRAS) to obtain cooperation towards the inclusion of FEBRAS vessels and other resources in the project database.
- ∞ Met with the management of CGGE International, a U.S. company which leases Russian research vessels, and arranged their cooperation to include relevant vessels in the ALIAS database.
- ∞ Continued and strengthened communication and coordination with UNOLS Arctic Icebreaker Coordinating Committee (AICC) through attendance of AICC meetings. Involvement in discussions about vessel availability and alternative vessel options clarified the role of the ALIAS database in the vessel-based research community and broadened contacts among vessel managers and science users.
- ∞ Presented a poster on the ALIAS vessel database at the 2004 Fall meeting of the American Geophysical Union (AGU) in connection with the AGU Ocean Sciences section, resulting in valuable contacts and increased community awareness of the project.
- ∞ Continued collaboration with VECO Polar Resources (VPR); as the logistics contractor for NSF-funded arctic research, VPR continues to be an important partner with ALIAS in data sharing, planning, and coordination.

Projected Activities

- ∞ Cultivate contacts made during this year to obtain less-accessible information on resources in Russia, Japan, China and Korea, with a priority on vessel information.
- ∞ Implement a search interface on the project website for vessel information.
- ∞ Continue to convene the advisory working group to guide the overall development of ALIAS.

The composition of the advisory group will be further developed in agreement with NSF arctic logistic support managers.

- ∞ Follow up on the agreement of advisory group members to provide scheduling and vessel description input.
- ∞ Expand site and record information to 130 records from the current 90, with emphasis on vessels and terrestrial research stations operated by Russia, Japan, China, and Korea. Strengthen collaboration and coordination with logistics-related organizations, data collection efforts, and related initiatives, such as Geographic Information Systems (GIS) development, the Circumarctic Environmental Observatories Network (CEON) initiative, the Integrated Ocean Drilling Program (IODP), and the International Polar Year (IPY), through formal presentations at relevant meetings, working group discussions, informal connections, and soliciting input from users and providers of logistics data.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace:

In the first half of this year, work on ALIAS was focused on expanding the vessel and cruise track database using information from known sources. In the latter part of the year (after the field season), efforts shifted towards collaboration and outreach, particularly on an international level, through meeting participation and presentations and direct contact with individuals, with the goal of accessing new sources for further expansion of the database. Overall ALIAS is moving towards increased international connections and increased awareness of the resources available, in direct pursuit of the project goal to provide an arctic logistics and collaboration tool.

1.3 Planning for Integrated Arctic Geographic Information Systems (GIS)

Continued development of the Arctic GIS Website and communications with a variety of GIS users and experts have supported continued coordination of ongoing Arctic GIS projects and programs, outreach and education activities, and Arctic GIS International Polar Year (IPY) planning.

Accomplishments

- ∞ Continued maintenance and development of Arctic GIS Website and Online Discussion Forum, including expansion of map and data web links and ongoing updates of news and events;
- ∞ Communications and collaboration with Arctic GIS community, including:
 - Collaborated with Matt Nolan, University of Alaska Fairbanks, on the use of EarthSLOT, a terrain and data visualization application, for education purposes; trained ARCUS staff person in use of EarthSLOT and created GIS visualization digital "movies" for teachers involved in the ARCUS education program, Teachers and Researchers—Exploring and Collaborating (TREC);
 - Collaborated with members of the Arctic GIS community regarding International Polar Year (IPY) planning and to draft an Arctic GIS IPY Letter of Intent.

Projected Activities

- ∞ Continue development of Arctic GIS website to include additional web links, news and events, and other relevant Arctic GIS resources;

- ∞ Support Arctic GIS community in IPY planning through continued website development, communications, and information dissemination.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None.

1.4a Study of Environmental Arctic Change (SEARCH) Coordination and Planning

During the latter part of this cooperative agreement year, the SEARCH science management function transitioned from the University of Washington to ARCUS. ARCUS worked with the NSF Program Director, SEARCH Science Steering Committee (SSC) Chair and committee members, and the past Science Management Office (SMO) at the University of Washington to implement this transition and plan for future activities. As part of this process, ARCUS developed and launched a new SEARCH website and initiated several coordination and logistics activities, including the planning for the May 2005 SEARCH Implementation Workshop.

Accomplishments

- ∞ Transitioned SEARCH website activities to ARCUS with a strong emphasis on a science-based website featuring SEARCH and SEARCH-related research:
 - Completed initial framework website, including redesign, framework pages for content, and development of functionality;
 - Worked with University of Washington SEARCH office to transition content to ARCUS-maintained website;
 - Compiled and created updated content for the website, including several SEARCH science pages featuring latest research and science news;
 - Worked iteratively with SEARCH SSC chair, the SSC, and others to refine and build website content and functionality in preparation for public launching;
 - Launched new SEARCH website March 2005.
- ∞ Developed materials, agendas, and provided staff support for SEARCH-related teleconferences beginning in November 2004, including approximately monthly teleconferences of the SEARCH Executive Committee.
- ∞ Worked with SEARCH SSC chair and Executive Committee to coordinate the process of populating SEARCH science implementation panels (Detecting Change Panel, Understanding Change Panel, and Responding to Change Panel).
- ∞ Began planning and coordination for the SEARCH Implementation Workshop, scheduled for May 2005 in Lansdowne, Virginia to establish priorities for the next steps of the implementation of SEARCH. Participants to include the SEARCH Science Steering Committee, implementation panels, SEARCH Interagency Program Management Committee (IPMC), and invited members of the arctic research community.
- ∞ Worked with SEARCH SSC Chair to draft and submit a SEARCH International Polar Year Letter of Intent.
- ∞ Completed the SEARCH Open Science Meeting proceedings; the document contains an executive summary, summaries of eight parallel sessions, meeting abstracts, and additional information about the Open Science Meeting.

Projected Activities

- ∞ Continue development, hosting, and maintenance of SEARCH website.

- ∞ Final printing and distribution of SEARCH Open Science Meeting proceedings.
- ∞ Planning and organization of SEARCH Implementation Workshop, 23-25 May 2005 in Lansdowne, Virginia:
 - Work with SEARCH SSC chair, executive committee, SEARCH panels, and NSF Program Director to develop focus, structure, and meeting materials for May 2005 SEARCH workshop;
 - Develop and maintain meeting website pages, including participant list, agenda, background materials, and community input tools;
 - Coordinate logistics of workshop and support meeting process;
 - Produce workshop report detailing SEARCH implementation priorities; final draft, community review, and publication planned for late June-early July 2005
- ∞ Develop SEARCH Geographic Information System database of SEARCH projects, related programs, and geographic areas for priority implementation needs.
- ∞ Transition management and development of SEARCH project database from the University of Washington to ARCUS; project database contains information on funded projects related to SEARCH science, including project personnel, abstract, activity area, and relevant weblinks; will expand database to include information on spatial/geographic focus of research.
- ∞ Continue to work with SEARCH SSC chair, Executive Committee, Panels, NSF Program Director, and broader SEARCH science community on appropriate science planning activities, including:
 - Identification of research and organizational priorities;
 - Developing processes for community input and development;
 - Workshop and conference organization and planning;
 - Supporting scientific program planning and implementation;
 - Collaboration with the International Study of Arctic Change (ISAC);
 - International Polar Year (IPY) planning;
 - Coordination with other related programs (CLIVAR, ASOF, CEON, etc.); and
 - Public outreach and education efforts.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace:

None.

1.4b SEARCH Open Science Meeting Student Support

Accomplishments

- ∞ No activities in the past year.

Projected Activities

- ∞ No activities are planned in the coming year.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None.

1.5 Planning for Bering Sea Research: Bering Ecosystem Study (BEST)

The NSF Arctic Sciences Section is supporting a planning process to initiate collaborative

studies of the sub-arctic seas, culminating in cooperative ecological research of the eastern, western and basin areas by Japan, Russia and the United States. The planning process began with the *Ecosystem Studies of the Sub-arctic Seas* workshop in September 2002, after which a nineteen-member working group was formed to begin development of a draft science plan. ARCUS was tasked to coordinate the March 2003 meeting of the working group, to provide staff support for the development of the science plan, and to publish and distribute the plan when completed.

Accomplishments

- ∞ Revised the draft science plan in response to comments received during community review, invited reviews, and town meetings in early 2004.
- ∞ Worked collaboratively and in support of science steering committee chair, Dr. George Hunt, to prepare the science plan in its final form for publication.
- ∞ Published 1,000 copies of the science plan in October 2004.
- ∞ Distributed copies of the science plan at the 2004 Arctic Climate Impact Assessment (ACIA) symposium, Arctic Council meetings, and other relevant Arctic-focused meetings.
- ∞ Distributed approximately 400 copies to-date in response to requests or to identified individuals and organizations. The science plan is also available as a PDF download on the ARCUS website.
- ∞ Updated and maintained the section of the ARCUS website designed to support the BEST planning process. The site includes information on previous and upcoming meetings and downloads of background materials, as well as the BEST science plan.
- ∞ Assisted Dr. Hunt and the Global Ocean Ecosystem Dynamics (GLOBEC) project office to plan and coordinate the BEST Implementation Workshop, planned in conjunction with the GLOBEC Symposium on Climate Variability and Sub-arctic Marine Ecosystems in Victoria, B.C., Canada, 16-20 May 2005. Coordinated travel funding provided for U.S. participants in the symposium. Funding will cover costs of invited speakers and, if sufficient funds are available, students.
- ∞ Assisted the appointment and convening of a BEST science steering committee and supported the electronic meetings and interactions of the committee for the preparation of a draft implementation plan.

Projected Activities

- ∞ Coordinate and support participant travel and provide staff support for the May 2005 BEST Implementation Workshop.
- ∞ Coordinate planning and logistics and provide travel support for a BEST science steering committee meeting in June 2005.
- ∞ Assist the chair and science steering committee members with the development and distribution of the draft BEST implementation plan.
- ∞ Continue distribution of the BEST science plan through hard copies and PDF download.
- ∞ Continue development of BEST website. Post new materials as they become available.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

Publication of the BEST science plan was delayed about two months from the planned date due to changes requested by Dr. Hunt.

1.6 Workshop, to be Determined

Accomplishments

- ∞ No activities in the past year.

Projected Activities

- ∞ No activities are planned in the coming year.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None.

1.7 Revision and Reprinting of the SEARCH Brochure

In 2001, ARCUS developed, printed and distributed 3,500 copies of a short informational brochure on the SEARCH program. Requests for the brochure exceeded the copies available, although the brochure is available as a PDF download on the ARCUS website.

Accomplishments

- ∞ At the request of NSF, 1,000 copies were printed in June 2004 and 300 copies were sent directly to NSF at their request. The reprinting of the brochure was considered a part of the SEARCH science management office activities and the cost is included in the budget for activity 1.4a Study of Environmental Arctic Change (SEARCH) Coordination and Planning.

Projected Activities

- ∞ Continue distribution of hard copies and availability of PDF download.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None.

1.8 Community Survey to Identify Arctic Research Data Coordination and Data Management Needs

Various arctic planning activities, conferences and meetings have identified a need for better information about arctic research data coordination and data management needs and problems—specifically for projects and programs that are inter-disciplinary, multi-institutional, international in scope, or interagency. ARCUS developed a community survey to assess community perspectives on data coordination issues using the online survey system that we have developed.

Accomplishments

- ∞ The survey tool has been designed and the online survey process is ready to be launched.

Projected Activities

- ∞ None.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

No further activities are expected at this time.

2. NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION

Work accomplished under this major task include a number of activities for the ARCSS Program and the Arctic Social Sciences Program, as well as the development of information and outreach materials for the Arctic Section as a whole.

2.1 ARCTIC SECTION SCIENCE MATERIALS

Accomplishments

- ∞ Coordinated community outreach and review for *Guidelines for Improved Cooperation between Arctic Researchers and Northern Communities*, drafted by the Arctic Sciences Section of the Office of Polar Programs at the National Science Foundation and the Barrow Arctic Science Consortium, with the input of the Alaska Eskimo Whaling Commission, North Slope Borough Department of Wildlife Management and the Alaska Native Science Commission.
 - Developed and published set of web pages to present content of draft report.
 - Published online survey to gather feedback on the draft document and forwarded comments to NSF Program Officer.
 - Printed 100 copies of the document for an Alaska Native Science Commission meeting in Anchorage, Alaska.
 - Posted PDF of report online.
- ∞ Developed and conducted online Arctic Section Proposal Target Date Survey. Community discussion about the timing of a new proposal deadline for the NSF Arctic Sciences Section led ARCUS to conduct this online survey of the U.S. arctic research community to get feedback on researchers' recommendations on the best timing for an annual deadline in future years.
 - Developed set of web pages for online survey, including graphical online results page.
 - 158 members of the research community submitted the online survey and results were forwarded to the NSF Arctic Sciences Section.

Projected Activities

- ∞ Update the "Arctic Science Discoveries" poster for NSF's Arctic Sciences Section to reflect timely research foci and results supported by the Arctic Sciences Section. Create digital versions of the poster for use by NSF for outreach purposes.
- ∞ Update the "Arctic Science Education: Partnerships Build Bridges Across the Learning Continuum" poster to reflect current education programs and activities supported by the Arctic Sciences Section. Create digital versions of the poster for use by NSF for outreach purposes.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None.

2.2 ARCTIC SYSTEM SCIENCE (ARCSS) PROGRAM COORDINATION

Over the past cooperative agreement year, the ARCSS Program has continued a focus on a synthesis effort aimed at achieving system-level understanding of the Arctic. Program coordination activities reported below have been designed to facilitate the synthesis effort, and have included increased community input and dialogue and development of a new ARCSS

Program science planning process. Planned activities will continue to facilitate a focus on system-level research and to continue fostering strong interdisciplinary collaboration.

2.2.1 ARCSS Coordination

Accomplishments:

- ∞ Worked with the ARCSS Committee (AC) chair to develop materials and agendas for near-monthly AC teleconferences.
- ∞ Worked with the ARCSS Committee and the ARCSS Program Director to facilitate and coordinate the development of a new ARCSS Announcement of Opportunity (AO) aimed at synthesizing knowledge of the arctic system. The AO is intended as another step in the ongoing ARCSS Program plan for a large-scale arctic synthesis effort.
- ∞ Coordinated and provided support for a writing group from the 2003 ARCSS Big Sky Synthesis Retreat to develop a scholarly paper reporting the findings of that retreat; paper was submitted by authors to *EOS*.
- ∞ Organized and convened the second ARCSS Synthesis Retreat in Tahoe City, California 8-14 August 2004. The weeklong science retreat built on the efforts of the 2003 Synthesis Retreat at Big Sky, Montana. The Tahoe Retreat began by focusing on the question that emerged from the Big Sky Retreat: "How realistic is a conceptual model of a two-state (modern and future seasonally ice free) arctic system, and how well do we understand the processes that may lead to a state change?" Both of the ARCSS Retreats were designed to bring together experts with knowledge about disparate elements of the arctic system to develop integrated knowledge about how the arctic operates as an integrated system. The Tahoe Retreat focused specifically on ways that humans fit into the arctic system. Twenty-eight scientists and graduate students representing a wide variety of scientific disciplines participated in the retreat.
- ∞ Worked with members of the ARCSS Committee to compile a packet of essential readings for the ARCSS Tahoe Synthesis Retreat. These twenty-six readings, annotated and organized into four key thematic areas, were bound together and provided to each Synthesis Retreat participant in advance of the meeting; a PDF file of the annotated bibliography was posted on the website for broad community use.
- ∞ Developed and implemented a community synthesis survey in advance of the ARCSS Tahoe Synthesis Retreat. The goal of the survey was to gather input from the scientific community about what scientific synthesis is and how an ARCSS synthesis can be effectively implemented.
- ∞ Facilitated the development of products emerging from the ARCSS Tahoe Synthesis Retreat.
- ∞ Began development of a new central ARCSS Science Management Office (SMO) designed to offer support and coordination to the scientific communities within the ARCSS Program. A major task currently underway for the new SMO is a central ARCSS website that will house information about the ARCSS Program and ARCSS research as well as links to other ARCSS-affiliated sites and current ARCSS funding opportunities.
- ∞ Under the auspices of the new SMO, began working with the investigators recently funded under the new ARCSS Study of Northern Alaska Coastal System (SNACS) program, including development of SNACS website.
- ∞ Began development of a searchable database of ARCSS-relevant research projects. The database, when complete, will be served across the Web via the new ARCSS website.

- ∞ Worked with several PIs, including two members of the ARCSS Committee, to develop a poster based on a HARC synthesis paper for presentation at the International Arctic Social Sciences Association (IASSA) Fifth International Congress of Arctic Social Sciences held in Fairbanks, Alaska in May 2004.
- ∞ In collaboration with the science management office for the NSF-funded Freshwater projects, reprinted 500 copies of the report CHAMP: *The Hydrologic Cycle and its Role in Arctic and Global Environmental Change: A Rationale and Strategy for Synthesis Study* due to continued communitywide demand for the publication. Over 250 of the reprint copies were distributed in response to prior requests and at a variety of arctic meetings and workshops, including the ARCUS 16th Annual Meeting and *Arctic Forum* and at the ARCSS Synthesis Retreat in Lake Tahoe.
- ∞ Developed and implemented an ARCSS Listserve to broadcast announcements about research initiatives, funding opportunities, meetings, and related activities focused on the ARCSS Program; the ARCSS Listserve has over 700 subscribers.
- ∞ Worked with ARCSS Committee to organize and hold the first ARCSS eTown Meeting in March 2005; the eTown Meeting enabled live audio web-conferencing, an online powerpoint presentation, polling, and private and public text chat, and was held to provide an open forum for discussion regarding ARCSS Program direction and planning. Forty-seven participants joined the online meeting.
- ∞ Planned and convened an ARCSS Committee meeting in March 2005 in Arlington, Virginia. The meeting was comprised of presentations from community representatives on arctic research activities as well as executive sessions to discuss a new ARCSS process and future planning priorities and outreach activities.
- ∞ Worked with ARCSS Committee to select and convene an ARCSS Executive Committee; the Executive Committee consists of a subset of members of the ARCSS Committee and will work closely with the ARCSS Committee chair and SMO to provide leadership for ARCSS science planning activities.

Projected Activities:

- ∞ Continue development and implementation of central ARCSS website. The website will include information about the ongoing ARCSS synthesis effort; up-to-date information about ARCSS meetings and workshops; a searchable database of NSF-funded arctic system research; information about past ARCSS research components; a searchable list of ARCSS publications; and other related resources.
- ∞ Continue development and implementation of a website for the new Study of Northern Alaska Coastal Systems (SNACS) program. This website will include public pages with information about each of the projects funded in this program as well as the investigators working on each. The site will also include password-protected pages to allow communication between and among the SNACS teams.
- ∞ Work with ARCSS Committee, NSF Program Director, and broader ARCSS research community to refine the science planning process for the ARCSS Program.
- ∞ Organize and convene a series of ARCSS eTown Meetings and other online input activities (e.g. surveys), as needed, to solicit community input into ARCSS planning and science priorities.

- ∞ Work with research community to organize and convene a series of ARCSS science seminars on scientific topics relevant to arctic system research, important scientific questions, or collaborative planning for research endeavors.
- ∞ Continue to communicate ARCSS Program updates and activities via ARCSS listserv and website.
- ∞ Work with ARCSS Committee and ARCSS research community to update the ARCSS Science Plan.
- ∞ Work with ARCSS Committee and NSF to rotate membership of the ARCSS Committee.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

The ARCSS Committee planning for the new ARCSS Program structure did not proceed as rapidly as initially anticipated in the past year. The development of the ARCSS science management office and the support efforts provided by the office were not as staff or time-intensive as had been planned until late in 2004.

2.2.2 ARCSS All-Hands Workshop 2002

Accomplishments

- ∞ No activities in the past year.

Projected Activities

- ∞ No activities are planned in the coming year.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None.

2.2.3 Coordinating a Human Dimensions of the Arctic System (HARC) Science Management Office

HARC coordination was subcontracted by ARCUS to the University of Alaska Fairbanks Center for Global Change (CGC) starting 1 July 2004. ARCUS has been working with new core office director Dr. Maribeth Murray, Associate Professor of Anthropology at the University of Alaska Fairbanks, to complete the transition of the HARC office from ARCUS to CGC and has continued to collaborate in planning and community development activities. The activities undertaken through this subcontract are reported as a separate section from ARCSS Coordination for clarity, though the costs of these activities are included in the ARCSS Coordination budget.

The HARC Core Office, in collaboration with ARCUS and relevant research communities, works to build the HARC community's research-capacity; synthesize HARC scientific knowledge and to integrate this knowledge into larger ARCSS syntheses efforts; refine and communicate the HARC research vision; and sustain active involvement in ongoing ARCSS Program planning.

Accomplishments

- ∞ Formed a HARC Science Steering Committee (SSC) representing a broad array of arctic researchers in both natural and social sciences; formal adoption is pending review by the

ARCSS Committee. The HARC SSC has been active via teleconference and face-to-face meetings.

- ∞ Participated in several relevant meetings and conferences for outreach and community development:
 - Presented two HARC papers at the *Fifth International Congress of Arctic Social Sciences (ICASS V)* meeting in Fairbanks, Alaska, May 2004.
 - Presented two HARC papers at the *55th Arctic Science Conference, Human Dimensions of the Arctic Environment, American Association for the Advancement of Science* in Anchorage, Alaska, September 2004.
 - Participated in the *12th Annual Arctic Conference: Archaeology, Anthropology, and Environmental Studies* in Washington, D.C., November 2004.
 - Presented HARC to CGC Steering Committee in Fairbanks, Alaska, September 2004.
 - Participated in *Marine Science in Alaska: 2005 Symposium* in Anchorage, Alaska, January 2005.
 - Participated in the *Alaska Forum on the Environment* in Anchorage, Alaska, February 2005, for the purpose of meeting with members of the Council of Athabascan Tribal Groups and the Alaska Native Science Commission.
 - Attended the *National Academies Open Meeting on Designing an Arctic Observation Network* in Anchorage, Alaska, February 2005. As a result of that meeting, the HARC SSC is drafting a statement on the importance of including a Human Dimensions (HD) component in the AON.
 - Participated in the *National Ecological Observing Network/High Latitude Ecological Observatory (NEON/HLEO) Open Meeting and Workshop* in Fairbanks, Alaska, February 2005.
- ∞ Assisted in coordination and distribution of HARC Special Issue of *Arctic*, published in December 2004.
- ∞ Initiated redesign and development of updated HARC website, to be hosted and maintained by ARCUS.

Projected Activities

- ∞ Continue to participate in relevant conferences for community coordination and outreach, including:
 - Present a HARC paper at *Human Security and Climate Change International Workshop* in Oslo, Norway, June 2005.
 - The HARC Core Office has organized two sessions for the *6th Open Meeting of the Human Dimensions of Global Environmental Change Research Community* in Bonn, Germany, October 2005. HARC sessions will be co-chaired by Maribeth Murray, HARC Core Office Director and Bruce Forbes, University of Lapland. Papers presented at the meeting will be prepared for peer-reviewed publication and as a republication series.
 - Present HARC poster at the *American Association for the Advancement of Science, 2005 Arctic Science Conference*, September 2005 in Kodiak, Alaska.
 - Participate in the *Second International Conference on Arctic Research Planning (ICARP II)*, November 2005 in Copenhagen, Denmark.
- ∞ Plan and coordinate one or more community webconferences in winter 2005/2006 to develop HARC and broader human-dimensions activities within the arctic research community.

- ∞ Publish and distribute a HARC brochure, detailing HARC and arctic human dimensions concepts, priorities, and developments in Fall 2005.
- ∞ Coordinate and administer a HARC Student Travel Award to provide a student conducting arctic human dimensions research the opportunity to present a paper/poster at an appropriate scientific meeting. Announcement of award planned for November 2005.
- ∞ Continue development of website to include information on HARC activities and HARC-related research efforts.
- ∞ Initiate inventory of HARC-related publications, to be entered into a database developed and maintained by ARCUS, with online access and search capabilities.
- ∞ Continue to work with HARC SSC and the broader community to develop HARC-related priorities and activities.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None.

2.2.4 Preparation and Publication of *CHAMP: The Hydrologic Cycle and its Role in Arctic and Global Environmental Change: A Rationale and Strategy for Synthesis Study*

Accomplishments

- ∞ This report was reprinted by request. See Activity 2.2.1 ARCSS Coordination.

Projected Activities

- ∞ No activities are planned in the coming year.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

The report was reprinted at the request of the Freshwater science management office, which shared the cost of the reprint.

2.3 ARCTIC SOCIAL SCIENCES PROGRAM COORDINATION

2.3.1 Arctic Social Sciences Coordination and Planning

Accomplishments

- ∞ In collaboration with the Alaska Native Science Commission (ANSC), planned and convened a workshop on *Partnering with Arctic Communities*, held as a two-day special session at the Fifth International Congress of Arctic Social Sciences (ICASS-V) in May 2004. In collaboration with the organizing committee, developed the final agenda; coordinated with ANSC and ICASS-V staff on workshop issues; facilitated travel and visa arrangements for presenters, many of them from Russia or rural Alaska; provided staff support for the workshop 22-23 May 2004.
- ∞ The *Partnering* workshop highlighted the best practices in the field and demonstrated to young researchers how to conduct respectful, cooperative research in arctic and other communities. Approximately 70 people attended.
- ∞ Discussed the development of appropriate post-workshop products with the ANSC, the NSF Arctic Social Sciences program manager, and the *Partnering* workshop participants.

Projected Activities

- ∞ No further activities are planned at this time.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None.

2.3.2 Translation and Publication of *Den Nye Sikkerhed - Groenland I Et Sikkerhedspolitisk Perspektiv* (The New Security: Greenland in a Security Political Perspective)

Accomplishments

- ∞ Ongoing distribution of *Grønland i et Sikkerhedspolitisk Perspektiv* at meetings, workshops, and by request.

Projected Activities

- ∞ Continue to distribute *Grønland i et Sikkerhedspolitisk Perspektiv* at meetings, workshops, and by request.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None.

2.3.3 Preparation and Publication of *The Earth is Faster Now: Indigenous Observations of Arctic Environmental Change*

Accomplishments

- ∞ Sold or distributed 137 copies of *The Earth is Faster Now*.
- ∞ Continued advertisement of the book through the ARCUS website.
- ∞ Sold copies of the book at a variety of arctic meetings and workshops, including the ARCUS 16th Annual Meeting and *Arctic Forum* and at the Alaska Math and Science Educators Conference.
- ∞ Held a book signing and reception at the Fifth International Congress of Arctic Social Sciences in May 2004.

Projected Activities

- ∞ Continue marketing and distribution.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None.

2.3.4 Humans in the Bering Sea Ecosystem Community Planning

ARCUS is supporting the development of a plan for social science research around the Bering Sea and the plan's integration with the Bering Sea Ecosystem Study (BEST) natural science plan. Throughout the autumn of 2003, as the BEST draft plan was introduced to the scientific community in a number of academic meetings, Alaska Natives and social scientists recognized that a critical human dimension was missing from the substantive goals of the draft plan. In order to complement the existing BEST science plan and to capitalize on interest in collaborations among resident communities and natural and social scientists, a committee was organized to

formulate a social science plan for the Bering Sea in early winter 2004, with support from the NSF Arctic Social Sciences Program. The goal of this plan is to establish responsible community-centered Bering Sea ecosystem research and partnerships between communities and researchers. The plan will be developed to serve the interests of the resident communities of the Bering Sea and to provide a model process for future collaborative research with Native communities. Towards that end, ARCUS was asked by the NSF Arctic Social Sciences Program Manager to assist in the organization and outreach activities related to science plan development. Working with the three-member steering committee and the Arctic Social Sciences Program Manager, ARCUS coordinated the Bering Sea Ecosystem Community Forum in Anchorage, Alaska in March 2004, with 27 participants.

Accomplishments

- ∞ Assisted the steering committee with arrangements for the "Humans and the Bering Ecosystem Town Meeting" held during the Fifth International Congress of Arctic Social Scientists (ICASS V) in May 2004.
- ∞ Coordinated a community planning process to develop a social science research plan for the Bering Sea in order to establish responsible community-centered Bering Sea ecosystem research and partnerships between communities and researchers. Provided support to the science advisory group to draft *Sustaining the Bering Ecosystem: A Social Sciences Plan*.
- ∞ Developed a section of the ARCUS website to support this planning process. The site includes background materials, a draft outline of the plan, and a form to provide comments on the draft to the organizing committee. In December 2004, an ArcticInfo message notified the community of this site and requested their comments on the draft.
- ∞ Distributed the hard copies of the draft to Bering Sea communities for review.

Projected Activities

- ∞ ARCUS will continue to support the planning process and community development of the science plan. The precise timing and scope of the tasks will be decided in collaboration with the organizing committee and Arctic Social Sciences Program Manager.
- ∞ Provide support and coordination for the science advisory group working with the Bering Ecosystem Studies (BEST) effort to work with Bering Sea communities to gather and integrate community recommendations into the BEST program.
- ∞ Convene a 20-30 person Bering Sea Community Forum to be held in conjunction with the Alaska Federation of Native conference in Fairbanks, Alaska in October 2005.
- ∞ Publish *Sustaining the Bering Ecosystem: A Social Sciences Plan*

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None.

3. ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION

ARCUS' education programs are developed around guiding principles that have been formulated over the past twelve years through several community workshops and our work with researchers, educators, students, and residents of the Arctic. These principles are:

- ∞ Education programs must be relevant, inquiry-based, and, if focused on K-12, they should align with National Science Education Standards.
- ∞ Education programs should build on existing education efforts; the community should focus

on increased collaborations between established programs and networks and should build supportive partnerships between researchers, educators and schools, and communities.

- ∞ Arctic residents must be involved in developing and implementing educational programs and outreach, and effective partnerships should be promoted and nurtured.
- ∞ There is a need for increased awareness or "visibility" of the arctic region and its residents, the unique and analogous aspects of the Arctic as a polar region, and its role in the Earth system.

All of ARCUS' education programs fit into this context and are developed to:

- ∞ Ensure that high-quality information and education in arctic science is available to the general public, students, teachers, and Natives of the Arctic.
- ∞ Enable interested and talented students to pursue scientific careers in the Arctic.
- ∞ Ensure that the scientific and technical workforce exists to meet the challenges of the arctic research agenda.

3.1 Arctic Science Education Activities

Accomplishments

No activities were undertaken in this general education category.

Projected Activities

None.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None.

3.2 Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series

ARCUS implemented an Arctic Visiting Speakers' (AVS) Series in January 2000 to increase communication and collaboration among the dispersed arctic research community and to nurture understanding and communication between arctic researchers and arctic community residents.

Accomplishments

- ∞ Nine speaking tours took place in the Series in the past year, addressing arctic issues at 54 different public engagements. Speakers presented at a variety of public venues including museums, schools, workshops, science fairs, and graduate seminars. A number of speakers held multi-day workshops for the public and conducted various media interviews (i.e., newspaper and radio).
- ∞ Over 2000 people attended the public presentations, a significant increase from the roughly 700 people attending the previous program year. The increase in attendance is largely due to three speaking tours that included multi-day workshops as part of their tour.
- ∞ Of the nine speaking tours, three speakers traveled from other countries to speak in the U.S. One U.S. speaker traveled to other countries. Five U.S. speakers visited institutions within the U.S.
- ∞ The topics covered included: Karelian folk culture; Native land claim issues, self-governance and capitalism; Inuit culture and indigenous law, Eskimo whaling and a changing arctic environment; hydrochemistry; and eco-hydraulics.

- ∞ Five new speakers were added to the Speaker's Bureau, which currently has 45 profiles for potential Arctic Visiting Speakers.
- ∞ Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series brochures were distributed at various conferences.

Projected Activities

- ∞ Continue to promote the use of the Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series to facilitate collaboration and information sharing about arctic research and the Arctic, including distribution of program information via Arctic Info and *Witness the Arctic*.
- ∞ Advertise the AVS series more extensively among arctic residents; encourage participation by indigenous experts as visiting speakers and by arctic communities as host institutions.
- ∞ Post AVS information to several educational email listserves around the country to stimulate interest from the K-12 education community to apply as host institutions.
- ∞ Support up to ten speaker tours in the next year.
- ∞ Continue to recruit individuals for the Speakers Bureau; however, host institutions are not restricted to inviting speakers from the Speakers' Bureau.
- ∞ Post updated information about speaker tours on the ARCUS website, including presentation videos and other materials sent to ARCUS by host institutions and speakers.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None.

3.3 Arctic Science Education Report

Accomplishments

- ∞ All print copies of the report have been distributed but we continue to receive many requests for it. The report is available electronically on the ARCUS website.

Projected Activities

- ∞ Continue to make the report available electronically.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None.

3.4 Arctic Alive!

In September 2001, ARCUS was awarded funding through the National Science Foundation's Directorate for Geosciences to develop and implement a pilot distance-delivery education program. *Arctic Alive!* allows students to "participate" in arctic research without leaving their classrooms. Through *Arctic Alive!*, students interact with researchers in remote arctic locations by using a variety of technologies. Using these technologies and corresponding curriculum, classrooms can simultaneously investigate the Arctic, discover careers in science, and research this unique and exciting world right along with the experts.

Accomplishments:

- ∞ *Arctic Alive!* brochures have been distributed at a number of arctic conferences and workshops as well as at several national science education conferences. It is also available electronically on the *Arctic Alive!* website.

- ∞ Elements of *Arctic Alive!* have been incorporated into the Teachers and Researchers Exploring and Collaborating (TREC) program, an educational research experience in which K-12 teachers participate in arctic research, working closely with scientists, as a pathway to improving science education through teachers' experiences in scientific inquiry (see Section 3.5. below).

Projected Activities

- ∞ Continue to incorporate elements of *Arctic Alive!* in existing ARCUS educational programs, such as TREC, to bring live science from the field to K-12 classrooms, educators, and the general public.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None.

3.5 Teachers and Researchers – Exploring and Collaborating (TREC)

The Teachers & Researchers - Exploring and Collaborating (TREC) program is an educational research experience in which K-12 teachers participate in arctic research, working closely with scientists, as a pathway to improving science education through teachers' experiences in scientific inquiry. TREC builds on the outstanding scientific and cultural opportunities of the Arctic to link research and education through intriguing topics that will engage students and the wider public. The main components of TREC include:

- ∞ *Arctic Field Research Experience*
The core of the TREC program is the field research experience, whereby TREC teachers participate in arctic field research for two or more weeks during spring/summer. Selected research projects represent the leading edge of scientific inquiry and include the K-12 teacher as integral part of science team.
- ∞ *Classroom and Public Connections*
Teachers and researchers connect with classrooms and the public through use of Internet tools such as online teacher and researcher journals, message boards, photo albums, real-time presentations and calls from the field, and online learning resources.
- ∞ *Professional Development*
TREC provides professional development opportunities for teachers who participate in field research projects as well as educators who connect through the Internet. TREC provides a variety of content, tools, and seminars geared towards subject matter learning, teaching practices, and alignment of TREC experiences with current professional and teaching standards.
- ∞ *Sustained Community and Support*
The TREC program is designed to extend the experience beyond field research to support a sustained community of teachers, scientists, and the public through online seminars, an e-mail listserv, and teacher-to-teacher peer groups.

TREC activities began in January 2004 and will continue through 2005.

Accomplishments

- ∞ Coordinated and supported 10 arctic teacher and research projects (TREC teams) for the 2004 spring/summer field season.

- ∞ Convened a management group in partnership with VECO Polar Resources and worked with the management group on coordinating logistical support for each TREC teacher.
- ∞ Coordinated and supported TREC team interactions and planning for the pre- and post- field portions of the TREC experience.
- ∞ Developed updated program materials, including program expectations and online seminar and website materials.
- ∞ Developed press materials to communicate TREC projects to public media outlets.
- ∞ Coordinated and supported TREC teacher deployment to the field and their ongoing (including in-field) communications with other educators, students and classrooms, and the public.
- ∞ Continued to refine and developed tools to facilitate the online collaboration between teachers, researchers, and the community, including webinars (real-time seminars broadcast over the Internet), bulletin board forums, chat capabilities, file sharing workspace, on-line calendar and field journals.
- ∞ Developed content and implemented a post-field webinar for participating 2004 TREC teams.
- ∞ Convened support groups for teachers, called Connecting Arctic/Antarctic Researchers and Educators (CARE), in collaboration with TEA (Teachers Experiencing the Antarctica/Arctic) staff, to provide a means by which science educators who have participated in research experiences can discuss relevant issues, such as classroom and pedagogical practices, professional development, integrating field research into the classroom, and curriculum development.
- ∞ Implemented the Arctic Science Education Listserve to communicate arctic science education activities and opportunities to a broad audience.
- ∞ Worked with TEA staff to develop two case study evaluations of TREC teachers to determine the success of the field research experience for positively affecting science teaching and learning in the classroom.
- ∞ Implemented application process for teachers and researchers for TREC 2005.
- ∞ Organized and convened a preliminary webinar for researchers to provide interested researchers more information about TREC program opportunities.
- ∞ Convened selection committee to select teachers and researchers from applicant pool.
- ∞ Selected and matched six (6) teacher and researcher teams for the 2005 field season.
- ∞ Developed new TREC website and online bulletin board with enhanced organizational, content, and security features. The TREC website supports teacher and researcher interactions, online interactive journaling and photo albums, information about the 2005 TREC research projects, and the development of the TREC learning resources database.

Projected Activities

- ∞ Conduct additional orientation webinars for TREC teams, focused on the development of educational resources and curriculum materials for participating teachers and researchers.
- ∞ Continue the development of the TREC website to support teacher interactions, online journaling and photo albums, information about the TREC research projects, and the development of the TREC learning resources database.
- ∞ Coordinate and support teacher and research project interactions and planning prior to the field portion of the TREC experience.
- ∞ Coordinate and convene an in-person orientation workshop for TREC teachers, including

safety training, technology training, and discussion and planning regarding classroom and outreach activities.

- ∞ Coordinate and support TREC teacher deployment to the field and their ongoing communications with other educators, students and classrooms, and the public.
- ∞ Implement the Virtual Campfire Chat program as TREC teachers and researchers return from their field research experiences. The Virtual Campfire Chats will be public internet-seminars, led by arctic researchers and educators on various topics of arctic research.
- ∞ Organize and convene the Arctic Learning Symposium at the conclusion of the year – a virtual conference where TREC teachers and researchers will share what they have learned from the experience, work together to integrate learning resources and curriculum materials developed during the year, and provide information to potential TREC participants and any individuals interested in using information developed through the TREC program.
- ∞ Implement a formative evaluation process to gather information about the application process, selection, accessibility, content, ease of use, involvement of underserved populations, and outreach to arctic residents.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None.

4. INFORMATION AND OUTREACH

4.1 *Witness the Arctic*: Chronicles of the NSF Arctic Sciences Program

Accomplishments

- ∞ Published and distributed 10,000 copies of *Witness the Arctic* (Winter 2004/2005, Volume 11, Number 2). This issue is a 32-page newsletter with a feature story that provides an overview of the Arctic Climate Impact Assessment (ACIA). The newsletter also includes a six-page insert on the arctic research projects of ARCUS member institution Oregon State University.
- ∞ *Witness the Arctic* currently has over 9,500 subscribers. Of these subscribers, 3,600 are outside the United States.
- ∞ The Winter 2004/2005 issue contains material from approximately 50 contributors, including academic researchers, program managers, agency personnel, educators, and facility managers, both U.S. and international.
- ∞ This issue is available for download on the ARCUS website.

Projected Activities

- ∞ Prepare and publish the Autumn 2005 issue of *Witness* (Volume 12, Number 1) with distribution planned for October 2005 for approximately 10,000 subscribers.
- ∞ Post the Autumn 2005 issue on the ARCUS website.
- ∞ Begin working on Spring 2006 of *Witness* (Volume 12, Number 2).

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None.

4.2 Website/Internet Resources

The ARCUS website provides essential information and resources for the very diverse and geographically distributed arctic research community and now serves over 6,000 files from over 2,000 pages. The website is the focal point for web-served educational programs such as TREC and *Arctic Alive!* and provides important information to the research community about important activities of key programs, for example SEARCH, the ARCSS Program, and BEST. The site also provides information about other scientific meetings and research community activities. Data and information is dynamically served from external 4D and MySQL databases and the site features dynamic, user created content through simple interfaces such as message boards and forums, photo albums, and calendars. Among many other resources, the website provides program information, electronic copies of publications, agenda, abstracts, and participant lists from arctic meetings, and audio and video archives from a variety of programs and meetings. The ARCUS website provides: information for the general public about arctic research; a forum for scientific exchange among arctic researchers; approaches for integrating arctic research with educational programs; access to other researchers, programs, and stakeholders working in the Arctic; viable ways to inform and involve arctic residents in research activities; and information about progress and recommendations related to various arctic research initiatives. In addition to content development for a variety of programs and activities, many improvements to the website structure and function were made in the past year. Users will benefit from ease of use through a more intuitive interface and vastly decreased page-load times due to these changes.

Accomplishments

- ∞ Redesigned or added major sections of the website to provide program information and to improve search functions, information delivery, and ease of information management. Website improvements for specific projects are discussed in the relevant project activity descriptions in this report.
- ∞ Developed and implemented a weblog communication application to provide means for invited guest authors to post essays and opinion pieces on issues relevant to arctic science.
- ∞ Posted draft reports related to arctic research activities, making them available for community review.
- ∞ Posted on-line versions of various arctic research publications, including all documents prepared by ARCUS, for easy access and downloading.
- ∞ Provided links to numerous arctic research websites, databases, planning processes, and other information of interest to the arctic research community.
- ∞ Improved navigation interface for subsections site-wide to provide more intuitive and efficient use of resources for users.
- ∞ Implemented a Google-powered whole-site search function, along with graphic enhancements throughout the website. The change has resulted in a more homogeneous environment throughout the site.
- ∞ Maintained, revised and improved upon PHP/MySQL powered applications that allow the use of open-source PHP scripted bulletin boards and other PHP-driven features for user-driven content and online database applications. Interactive bulletin boards support such programs as the SEARCH, *Arctic Alive!* and TREC, Arctic GIS, the ARCSS Program.
- ∞ Reorganized and streamlined server topology in order to enhance both form and function.
- ∞ Removed approximately 250,000 lines of code throughout the site, helping to reduce both download time and web development time.

- ∞ Formulated and began to implement a plan to bring the entire site up to W3C's XHTML Transitional code compliance standards.
- ∞ Began to migrate the fundamental layout of the standard code base away from tables, utilizing instead cascading style sheets. This creates a distinct separation of content and presentation, which in turn reduces development time.
- ∞ Implemented an ARCUS "Wiki," which facilitates the smooth flow of information and inter-office communication among the web development team members and project management staff.

Projected Activities

- ∞ Develop a new ARCSS Program website, including site design and program content, reflecting the integrated ARCSS science management structure.
- ∞ Finish the upgrade of the standard code base to XHTML Transitional to bring the entire website in line with accessibility standards.
- ∞ Create XML-based solutions for future event documentation and information. This will allow for improved data encapsulation and greater flexibility of presentation. It will also enhance the portability and relative ease of cross-platform distribution of information.
- ∞ Catalog and label images site-wide to effectively include title and description information within the XHTML.
- ∞ Continue to maintain, manage, and update this large, dynamic, and high traffic website.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None.

4.3 Arctic Info Listserve

Accomplishments

- ∞ Received, reviewed, accepted or declined, edited, and formatted over 300 submissions to ArcticInfo.
- ∞ Distributed 277 announcements including notices on funding opportunities, important events, publications, and position announcements. On average, over 32 announcements were posted per month.
- ∞ Communicated with subscribers regarding announcements, special information requests, manual subscribe or unsubscribe requests, and other concerns.
- ∞ Maintained a searchable, online archive of all announcements posted.
- ∞ The listserv had 324 new subscribers resulting in 4,628 current subscribers.
- ∞ Maintained a database to track subscription activity.
- ∞ Managed the "bounce list" by researching bounced announcements to correct and update addresses, investigate apparently dead domains, and delete addresses that consistently bounced back from the subscriber list.
- ∞ Performed software maintenance and upgrade. The list server software was replaced with a new software package called LetterRip Pro 4.0. In addition to running natively under Mac OS X 10.3, it includes a dedicated built-in server optimized for processing and sending list messages, allowing for a far more efficient distribution process. In addition, a new web-based administration page allows better viewing and management of current subscribers and maintenance of the subscriber list itself. A new process utilizing web-forms for the end-user

or potential subscriber offers a browser-based method of subscribing and unsubscribing while providing ARCUS with useful user-supplied information for the subscriber database.

- ∞ There have been 1,812 announcements distributed from ArcticInfo since its creation in September of 1996. Each year has seen an increase in submissions for distribution and in subscribers.

Projected Activities

- ∞ Continue to review, edit, and format submissions. Post new announcements to the list and add them to the online archive.
- ∞ Continue to communicate with subscribers and organizations and individuals who wish to use the list for information distribution or access.
- ∞ Continue to track subscription activity and research "bounced" addresses.
- ∞ Continue advertising, maintenance, and management of the list.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None.

4.4 The Directory of Arctic Researchers

Accomplishments

- ∞ Added 210 new records between April 2004 and March 2005. As of March 2005, there were a total of 3,961 individual records in the Directory. Surveyed researchers with current directory records to get updated contact and current research information.
- ∞ Surveyed significant international research organizations and individuals to expand non-U.S. researcher records in the database.
- ∞ Maintained and regularly updated a downloadable PDF of the Directory including alphabetically listed individual researcher entries and a cross-reference file listing researchers by name within science specialty categories. Developed a new Directory PDF design and creation process, which streamlined the PDF creation and makes a smaller document and file size.

Projected Activities

- ∞ Implement an automated daily update of the online Directory, which will include an automated daily Directory PDF creation and uploading process.
- ∞ Develop web services to allow interactions (pulling and pushing information) with other arctic databases such as the CEON-IMS, Barrow Area Information Database-Internet Map Server, and the VECO Polar Resources ARLSS project database.
- ∞ Develop and populate a new directory section for educators, which includes identifying individuals and groups for inclusion, sending survey forms, updating individual records for the database, and developing new search features on the Directory website.
- ∞ Continue maintenance and expansion of the on-line directory.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None.

4.5 Internet Graphics Archive (Internet Media Archive)

Accomplishments

- ∞ Set up a dedicated server for the storage and distribution of all resources contained in the Internet Graphics Archive—a collection of photos, graphics, videos, and presentations that have been collected for various purposes and will be shared through the Internet—now renamed the Internet Media Archive.
- ∞ Evaluated and tested a variety of potential software packages for the archive and selected the most viable.
- ∞ Installed and modified the online database software for hosting the archive. The software includes a powerful search function by keyword, and allows for easy categorization, access and downloading. The selected software allows multiple types of media to be posted (photos, graphics, video), allows different levels of administrative access, and uses a point and click search feature.
- ∞ Developed a watermark logo to prevent the unauthorized use of certain photos. This logo is in use now and was approved by the photographers before posting their photos to the archive.
- ∞ Sorted photos and other resources now in the ARCUS collection for duplicates and categorized them by submitter/photographer. Placed photos into spreadsheets for better organization.
- ∞ Developed a control sheet to gather key information about the photos and other graphical or media resources to be posted into the archive; distributed the spreadsheet to gather standardized and organized information about the media resources.
- ∞ Developed a legal permissions document to grant ARCUS permission to post these resources on the Internet. The permissions document allows various types of reproduction authorization:
 - Free with no restrictions or other requirements.
 - Free, but proper credit or attribution is required.
 - Free, but the creator must be notified about the use.
 - Free, but no modifications are allowed without permission.
 - A per-use fee is required; contact the creator to arrange for use and payment.
- ∞ Posted all photos for which permission has been received to the online archive, with detailed photo information, photographer contact information, use criteria, and keywords for the search interface.
- ∞ The Internet Media Archive currently contains over 1,700 photos and other media resources.

Projected Activities

- ∞ Continue to gather and add to the collection of arctic-related images and other media resources.
- ∞ Continue research and data entry of relevant information about source, subject, dates, research project, and funding source for all of the images.
- ∞ Maintain communication with the contributors and potential contributors to solicit contributions and timely and detailed information about the media resources.

- ∞ Obtain use permissions, attribution, and detailed information for the entire ARCUS image collection.
- ∞ Archive the extensive ARCUS collection of video resources from various workshops and scientific meetings and education and outreach activities.
- ∞ Identify or produce additional figures, cartoons, photographs, and maps depicting arctic research-related information. Develop short abstracts that explain each scientific figure and that provide information necessary for attribution, as well as citations for source material and other related references.
- ∞ Finalize the public interface and tools, announce the resource via ArcticInfo, and make the Internet Media Archive available to the research community through the ARCUS website.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

After a hiatus of several years, intensive work on the Internet Media Archive began in November 2004 and excellent progress has been made to-date. We anticipate continued progress and ongoing development at the same rapid pace over the coming year.

4.6 Arctic Community Outreach

Accomplishments

- ∞ Planned and hosted a two-day *Arctic Forum* in conjunction with ARCUS' 16th Annual Meeting in Arlington, VA in May 2004. The *Forum* was attended by 112 participants, including arctic researchers from the U.S. and other countries, policy makers, federal agency personnel, and arctic residents.
 - The Forum was chaired by Dr. Wieslaw Maslowski of the Naval Postgraduate School and Dr. Mark Serreze of the Cooperative Institute for Research in Environmental Sciences (CIRES) at the University of Colorado Boulder, and focused on the topic *Recent Decrease of the Arctic Sea Ice: Its Causes, Consequences, and Historical Perspective*.
 - Keynote addresses included presentations by Warren Matumeak, a Native Elder of Barrow, Alaska; Mark Serreze, the Cooperative Institute for Research in Environmental Sciences at the University of Colorado; and a student presentation by one of the winners of the student poster competition at the SEARCH Open Science Meeting in October 2003. The *Forum* also featured a panel discussion, moderated by Dr. David Klein from the Institute of Arctic Biology, University of Alaska Fairbanks, on forming partnerships and collaboration in arctic research.
 - The 2004 *Arctic Forum* featured 17 oral presentations and 24 posters. Information was presented on research funded by NSF, arctic research supported by other federal agencies or programs, and significant international arctic research efforts.
- ∞ Developed information resources regarding arctic research activities, needs, and priorities and participated in outreach activities at scientific meetings and workshops to inform the broader scientific community and key policy and decision-makers about important arctic research efforts and findings.
- ∞ Participated in or sponsored arctic outreach activities at the September 2004 AAAS Arctic Science Conference in Anchorage, Alaska, at the Fall 2004 Meeting of AGU in San Francisco, California, and at other relevant meetings and workshops throughout the year.

Projected Activities

- ∞ Publish and distribute the 2004 and 2005 *Arctic Forum* abstract volumes.
- ∞ Convene a two-day *Arctic Forum* in conjunction with ARCUS' 17th Annual Meeting in Washington, DC in May 2005. The focus of the *Arctic Forum* 2005 will be *Arctic Climate Change and Public Literacy: What's at Stake?* Dr. Stephanie Pfirman of the Department of Environmental Science at Barnard College and Dr. Bruce Forbes of the Arctic Centre at the University of Lapland will chair the 2005 *Arctic Forum*.
- ∞ Presentations at the 2005 *Arctic Forum* will include a diverse range of perspectives and will address such topics as: current science on arctic climate change and future scenarios; public perception of arctic climate change; communication strategies and their effectiveness; and the role of the research community in public literacy.
- ∞ Prepare posters or presentations on request and participate in major scientific meetings or workshops to provide information and outreach regarding arctic research activities, needs, and priorities.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None.

4.7 Publication: *The Arctic*

A need has long existed for a publication that introduces the environments and peoples of the Arctic and is scientifically accurate and relevant while remaining comprehensible to the general public, including middle and high school students. To address this need, ARCUS began developing an overview of the arctic region for a general audience in 2001, with funding through the previous cooperative agreement with NSF. Tentatively titled *The Arctic: Changes in a Polar Region*, this book is similar to a magazine in the quality of graphics and level of complexity and will be accessible to a wide range of readers. The contents and the publication design and layout are targeted to the general public and middle and high school students. The contents cover ocean, terrestrial, and human components of the Arctic and review various aspects of these domains, including contemporary and historical research, through a seasonal framework. Links among important arctic processes and between the biophysical systems and human cultures are illustrated.

Accomplishments

- ∞ Further work on this publication was delayed due to the high demand for staff resources to be dedicated to other projects, primarily the Bering Ecosystem Study (BEST) science plan.

Projected Activities

- ∞ Revise draft in response to comments received during invited review.
- ∞ Research and purchase photo rights for photos selected for the final publication.
- ∞ Prepare final versions of special graphics for publication.
- ∞ Publish in October 2005 and make the initial print run of 5,000 copies available for public information requests and educational uses. The publication also will be available electronically via the ARCUS website.
- ∞ ARCUS plans to market this publication so that additional copies can be printed upon demand without securing additional funding from NSF.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

Completion of this publication was postponed in order to direct staff resources to other more urgently needed projects.

4.8 Eider Endangered Species Consultation Bulletin

Accomplishments

∞ None in the past year.

Projected Activities

∞ None expected at this time.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None.

5. CORE SUPPORT

Core support provides management and infrastructure crucial to support the overall tasks and the projects and activities included in each task of the cooperative agreement. This category was initiated to ensure stability and continuity of the direct activities that support the whole of the cooperative agreement so they are not vulnerable to the changes in the specific tasks and activities funded from year-to-year through the agreement.

ARCUS is a relatively small non-profit organization and the Executive Director is intimately involved in all activities of the organization including planning, prioritizing, managing, and directly implementing the work undertaken on behalf of the National Science Foundation. The Executive Director works closely with ARCUS project managers to prioritize tasks with respect to annual and longer-term plans and to manage individual workloads and projects. She closely reviews activities and products and ensures that projects are completed as scheduled and in accordance with the annual plan and that the products or effects of the activities are beneficial to arctic research and to the goals of the particular task funded through the cooperative agreement. She is directly involved in working with outside committees and contributors to ensure that projects are concluded effectively and in a timely fashion. The Executive Director also works closely with the ARCUS Business Manager in budgeting and reviewing ongoing project expenditures against the NSF budget. The Executive Director liaises directly with NSF on all planning, programmatic, and budget issues. This component of management is essential to the ongoing work ARCUS carries out on behalf of NSF.

Similarly, the Systems Administrator manages the network, server, and all technical needs required to support NSF tasks and project activities. He works directly with the Executive Director to ensure that all hardware and software requirements are met so that server and network operations supporting NSF activities are carried out smoothly and efficiently. The Executive Director and Systems Administrator plan for upcoming needs, including scientific meetings and conferences convened by ARCUS on behalf of the NSF, in conjunction with the annual program plan.

While the work of both these positions is directly related to the successful implementation of NSF activities and projects, it is more difficult to allocate much of this time specifically to any one individual project, hence the use of Core Support to collect these direct overarching management and infrastructure costs. Other costs charged to Core Support include direct system infrastructure (computer hardware and software required to maintain the network and server needed to support the database and listserv, NSF sponsored tasks), high-speed Internet, governmental liaison office in Washington, D.C., and the development necessary to continuously maintain the level of service committed to the arctic research community under the cooperative agreement.

Accomplishments

- ∞ Coordinated planning, managed emerging priorities, and supervised work on all the tasks and project activities described in this report. The portion of the Executive Director's time dedicated to project activities funded through this agreement is charged to the Core Support category.
- ∞ Upgraded hardware, software, and programming to expand capability for projects that require expanded server, network, and database capacity, support for NSF-sponsored meeting online registration, poster submission, and general information distribution.
- ∞ Managed the server setup, network, creation of needed technical resources, and the computing capability that directly supports the project activities. The portion of the System Administrator's time dedicated to project activities funded through this agreement is charged to the Core Support category. System upgrades included:
 - Developed a new website structure using a Server Side Include function of the 4D WebStar V web server which allows for creating a centralized header navigation page that is automatically inserted on every page before being sent out to the clients browser. Designed using a combination of javascript and PHP, the new header navigation includes an integrated search function using the Google API, a site-wide frequent links navigation system, and randomly generated background image rotator. Now, by modifying a single HTML page the entire look of the site can be changed or features added, a far better solution than the previous structure in which a single site-wide design change would require manually editing hundreds of individual HTML pages.
 - Increased the development and use of PHP/MySQL-based applications for the website for both client applications such as interactive bulletin board systems, search capabilities, and internal collaborative tools such as the newly created "wiki" system for web development organization. The use of PHP has offered numerous possibilities for the improvement and advancement of the website.
 - Upgraded the Domain Name Server system to a newer version of the Quick DNS software package. Running natively under Mac OS X and using the built-in industry standard BIND 9 DNS system with a GUI configuration application provides for increased security options and increased stability. Our ISP also recently upgraded their DNS systems, so a faster propagation of DNS data to the world is possible; it now takes a matter of hours to reflect even a small change vs. days.
 - Upgraded the 4D Mail email system with a series of small upgrades and adjustments. ARCUS is acting as a beta test site for 4D Mail and 4D WebStar V giving us access to the newest versions of the software for testing and bug fix purposes in addition to allowing for user-supplied input for future changes to the software

- Installed a new PHP based webmail application that has considerably improved the user experience for webmail. By accessing the users mailbox directly without an intermediate step of moving mail to a backend database, the PHP based system is faster and more stable than the previously used 4D WebMail application. TREC teachers and researchers use ARCUS webmail, as do other project activities that require email addresses on the ARCUS system, as well as ARCUS staff.
- The computer network backup system was upgraded to a much larger capacity to deal with the increasing amounts of data generated by an ever-increasing number of projects, staff, and server machine capacity. The rack mount Xserve storage capacity was increased from 480GB of available storage to 930GB of storage; an additional Xserve with a capacity of 1TB of storage was added, making it possible to fully back up every single server and client machine on the network with 1/2 terabyte of expansion capacity. Full and complete backups of every machine make it much easier to fully restore a damaged machine or system if computers suffer a serious hardware problem.
- Upgraded the Filemaker Server application (the server that runs the ARCUS database and Directory of Arctic Researchers) and set up a dedicated server machine to improve performance. The upgrade from the previous version 5.5 to the new version 7.0 Advanced increased performance to client machines and added capability to doing web-publishing of the databases for searching and editing of content from a standard web browser. The Advanced feature pack also allows for future tighter integration between the 4D 2004 database system (which runs the online Directory of Arctic Researchers) and the Filemaker 7 database system allowing for automatic updating of data across the systems providing for more consistent data sets and automated 'live' access of data in the Filemaker Server from 4D web applications.
- Set up a dedicated server for the Internet Media Archive. High capacity RAID-mirrored drives and a built-in Apache web server with PHP 5 and MySQL modules and the Quicktime Streaming Server allow for a high-speed distribution platform dedicated entirely to media files. This takes the load of serving large bandwidth video files and the growing Internet Media Archive off the primary server while providing ample storage for the expanding collection of media assets. The server is also set up for Internet streaming of workshops and meetings.
- The list server software was replaced with an entirely new software package called LetterRip Pro 4.0. The new server is easier to administer and allows for creation of multiple mailing lists. New lists that have been created and hosted since acquiring the new software include:
 - ✎ The Arctic Education Mailing List, a participatory list dedicated to providing a venue for educators, researchers, and learners to exchange information about opportunities, challenges, methods, resources, important events, and other useful topics.
 - ✎ The HARC Mailing List which is a broadcast-only list for creating announcements relating to the ARCSS Program Human Dimensions of the Arctic or HARC activities.
 - ✎ The BALI List which is the Barrow Area Logistics Information List Serve, a list for distribution and discussion about logistics needs and resources in the Barrow area.
- The internal file sharing file server was upgraded to a new system with added facilities for FTP access. This server acts as the DHCP server for the entire network providing IP addresses for wireless computers and any connected guest machines and includes a timeserver for more accurate syncing of system clocks on the local network.

- ∞ Supported staff training to increase technical expertise for managing the dynamic and automated portions of the website and databases.
- ∞ Supported staff travel to arctic research meetings and workshops that addressed topics pertaining to multiple NSF projects and activities included in the cooperative agreement, but which were not specific to one project.
- ∞ Concluded government liaison work at our Washington, D.C. office and consolidated remaining workflow and processes into the Fairbanks office.

Projected Activities

- ∞ Coordinate planning, prioritization and supervision of work on all the tasks and projects described in the projected activities, the program plan and budget for 2005-2006. The portion of the Executive Director's time dedicated to project activities funded through this agreement will be charged to the Core Support category.
- ∞ Continue to research and upgrade hardware, software and programming required to expand the interactive and dynamic capabilities of such projects as ALIAS, Arctic GIS, SEARCH, the ARCSS Program, TREC, the Directory of Arctic Researchers, Arctic Info, the Calendar, the Internet Media Archive, interactive real-time online seminars and meetings, interactive bulletin boards, meeting registration and abstract submission, streamed audio and video content, and general information.
- ∞ Manage the server setup, network, creation of needed technical resources, and the computing capability that directly supports the project activities. The portion of the System Administrator's time dedicated to direct activities funded through this agreement will be charged to the Core Support category.
- ∞ Support staff participation at arctic research meetings and workshops on topics pertaining to multiple NSF projects and activities included in the cooperative agreement, but which are not specific to one project.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None.

SUMMARY

ARCUS has facilitated scientific planning for arctic research efforts for over fourteen years by working with the scientific community through surveys, workshops, Internet communications, and other means to define science priorities and research initiatives. ARCUS has organized dozens of workshops and published numerous scientific planning documents that reflect the recommendations of the arctic research community on scientific priorities in various research fields. All of the activities described in this program plan support the community science planning process for the NSF Arctic Sciences Section and provide information and support for the conduct of arctic research and, therefore, will contribute to the overall excellence and advancement of arctic research supported by the National Science Foundation.

Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.

Attachment A

OPP-0101279

Total Costs by Category

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	Original 5-year Budget	5 Year Cumulative Budget	Year 1 Actuals	Year 2 Actuals	Year 3 Actuals	Year 4 Actuals	Year 4 Funds Remaining	Proposed Year 5 Budget
1 ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING								
1.1 Arctic Logistics	388,437	97,294	19,067	23,874	53,130	1,123	2,176	100
1.2 ALIAS Website	480,011	574,562	96,470	128,701	140,337	86,171	57,515	122,883
1.3 GIS Planning	50,082	66,412	35,461	100	14,240	4,312	19,570	12,299
1.4a SEARCH Planning	64,915	689,589	-	6,298	307,034	20,027	39,183	356,231
1.4b SEARCH OSM Student Support	-	28,776	-	-	28,776	-	-	-
1.5 Bering Sea Planning	66,304	166,573	-	32,877	54,615	13,863	(1,912)	65,218
1.6 Workshop TBD	67,846	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
1.7 SEARCH Brochure	-	5,741	5,741	-	-	-	-	-
1.8 Arctic Data Survey	-	7,485	-	-	1,335	6,150	2,922	-
SubTotal Direct Costs	1,117,593	1,636,432	156,738	191,850	599,468	131,645	119,454	556,731
Indirect Costs	470,507	606,744	62,769	67,492	218,143	49,633	58,340	208,708
TOTAL	1,588,100	2,243,176	219,507	259,342	817,611	181,278	177,794	765,438
2 NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION								
2.1 Arctic Section Science Materials	24,782	21,523	7,040	2,805	1,083	1,333	6,703	9,263
2.2 ARCSS Program Coordination								
2.2.1 ARCSS Coordination	225,670	1,140,215	30,274	117,883	239,688	311,686	331,686	440,684
2.2.2 ARCSS All-Hands Workshop	147,106	305,498	259,825	42,447	3,226	-	-	-
2.2.3 HARC SMO	151,980	165,344	44,449	29,400	91,495	0	(0)	-
2.2.4 Arctic Hydrology Report	11,543	18,276	18,276	-	-	-	-	-
SubTotal 2.2 Direct Costs	536,299	1,629,333	352,824	189,730	334,409	311,686	331,686	440,684
2.3 ASSP Program Coordination								
2.3.1 Arctic Social Sciences Planning	64,060	96,235	6,466	7,856	70,519	4,775	(2,075)	6,620
2.3.2 Greenland Book	19,543	12,263	12,263	-	-	-	-	-
2.3.3 Arctic Social Sciences Volume	-	40,059	15,933	23,171	954	-	-	-
2.3.4 Bering Sea Community Planning	-	69,062	-	-	15,401	6,437	23,888	47,224
SubTotal 3.3 Direct Costs	83,602	217,619	34,662	31,027	86,875	11,212	21,813	53,844
Sub-Total Direct Costs	663,176	1,868,476	394,525	223,562	422,367	324,230	360,202	503,791
Indirect Costs	279,197	548,267	147,513	67,999	107,665	95,665	157,872	129,425
TOTAL	942,373	2,416,743	542,038	291,561	530,033	419,895	518,074	633,216
3 ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION								
3.1 Arctic Science Education Activities	75,444	18,846	10,847	7,999	(0)	-	-	-
3.2 Arctic Visiting Speakers Program	175,681	131,304	37,130	21,671	24,064	23,117	1,342	25,322
3.3 Arctic Science Education Report	-	22,919	7,691	15,228	-	-	-	-
3.4 ARCTIC ALIVE!	-	27,996	-	-	27,996	-	-	-
3.5 TREC	-	171,214	-	-	36,291	58,905	(8,092)	76,019
SubTotal Direct Costs	251,125	372,279	55,668	44,898	88,350	82,021	(6,750)	101,341
Indirect Costs	105,724	140,958	22,244	16,888	32,397	30,919	1,447	38,510
TOTAL	356,849	513,237	77,913	61,786	120,748	112,941	(5,303)	139,850
4 INFORMATION AND OUTREACH								
4.1 Witness the Arctic Newsletter	302,879	368,300	53,943	84,978	46,540	77,513	22,512	105,327
4.2 Web Site/Internet Resources	372,565	510,497	68,740	54,936	89,307	124,830	(36,918)	172,683
4.3 Arctic Info Listserv	98,790	77,319	12,508	12,286	20,013	21,919	(1,939)	10,595
4.4 Directory of Arctic Researchers	39,305	52,756	8,087	17,428	9,319	8,671	4,359	9,250
4.5 Internet Graphics Archive	63,750	86,770	-	13,734	424	16,730	10,511	55,881
4.6 Community Outreach	208,890	344,541	46,871	53,802	50,480	88,431	(40,378)	104,957
4.7 Publication: The Arctic	-	48,326	619	55	-	83	53,588	47,569
4.8 Endangered Species Bulletin	-	2,617	2,150	468	-	-	-	-
SubTotal Direct Costs	1,086,179	1,491,127	192,917	237,686	216,084	338,177	11,735	506,263
Indirect Costs	457,281	558,848	76,130	84,622	78,132	127,584	22,878	192,380
TOTAL	1,543,460	2,049,975	269,047	322,308	294,216	465,761	34,613	698,643
5 CORE SUPPORT								
Core Support								
SubTotal Direct Costs	1,426,996	1,495,019	262,598	269,426	322,376	334,580	(13,074)	306,040
Indirect Costs	600,765	556,741	103,275	95,633	115,629	125,909	12,338	116,295
TOTAL	2,027,761	2,051,760	365,873	365,059	438,005	460,489	(736)	422,335
TOTAL COSTS	6,458,543	9,274,891	1,474,377	1,300,056	2,200,612	1,640,364	724,441	2,659,482

Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.
OPP-0101279
NSF Task & Activity Summary

Attachment B

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	Original 5-year Budget	5 Year Cumulative Budget	Year 1 Actuals	Year 2 Actuals	Year 3 Actuals	Year 4 Actuals	Year 4 Funds Remaining	Proposed Year 5 Budget
1 Arctic Community Science Planning								
1.1 ARCTIC LOGISTICS								
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	109,509	62,795	9,479	20,457	31,822	1,037	2,061	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	32,140	7,965	4,127	2,077	1,761	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	165,620	3,238	2,634	604	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	81,168	23,296	2,828	736	19,547	85	115	100
Total direct costs	388,437	97,294	19,067	23,874	53,130	1,123	2,176	100
Indirect Costs	163,532	35,526	7,582	8,437	19,043	426	993	38
Total direct and indirect costs	551,968	132,820	26,649	32,311	72,174	1,548	3,168	138
1.2 ALIAS WEBSITE								
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	387,761	385,311	60,048	80,628	101,646	66,377	31,039	76,613
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	80,350	66,198	14,437	14,164	11,272	10,055	6,215	16,270
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	1,254	-	1,254	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	11,900	121,799	21,985	32,656	27,419	9,739	20,261	30,000
Total direct costs	480,011	574,562	96,470	128,701	140,337	86,171	57,515	122,883
Indirect Costs	202,084	212,212	37,900	45,517	49,653	32,448	29,337	46,695
Total direct and indirect costs	682,095	786,774	134,370	174,218	189,990	118,619	86,852	169,578
1.3 GIS PLANNING								
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	13,282	39,166	20,920	-	4,936	4,265	16,363	9,045
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	5,548	2,294	-	-	-	3,254	3,254
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	7,000	9,688	8,050	-	1,638	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	29,800	12,010	4,196	100	7,666	47	(47)	-
Total direct costs	50,082	66,412	35,461	100	14,240	4,312	19,570	12,299
Indirect Costs	21,084	26,548	14,902	34	5,323	1,615	8,654	4,674
Total direct and indirect costs	71,166	92,960	50,363	134	19,563	5,927	28,224	16,973
1.4a SEARCH PLANNING								
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	16,536	263,364	-	729	79,131	9,948	20,508	173,556
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic and foreign)	3,204	50,105	-	3,312	16,241	552	2,702	30,000
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	31,725	134,884	-	225	44,180	980	(980)	89,500
Other Direct Costs	13,450	241,235	-	2,031	167,481	8,548	16,952	63,175
Total direct costs	64,915	689,589	-	6,298	307,034	20,027	39,183	356,231
Indirect Costs	27,329	255,475	-	2,171	113,207	7,579	17,881	132,518
Total direct and indirect costs	92,244	945,064	-	8,469	420,240	27,606	57,064	488,749
1.4b SEARCH OSM Student Support								
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Permanent Equipment	250	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic and foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	27,945	-	-	27,945	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	831	-	-	831	-	-	-
Total direct costs	250	28,776	-	-	28,776	-	-	-
Indirect Costs	-	10,757	-	-	10,757	-	-	-
Total direct and indirect costs	250	39,533	-	-	39,533	-	-	-
1.5 BERING SEA PLANNING								
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	17,250	56,435	-	3,919	23,081	16,665	(7,714)	12,771
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	3,254	12,390	-	8,205	(825)	-	-	5,010
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	32,350	58,253	-	19,749	(3,508)	-	-	42,012
Other Direct Costs	13,450	39,494	-	1,004	35,867	(2,802)	5,802	5,425
Total direct costs	66,304	166,573	-	32,877	54,615	13,863	(1,912)	65,218
Indirect Costs	27,914	61,006	-	11,333	19,662	5,228	(89)	24,783
Total direct and indirect costs	94,218	227,579	-	44,210	74,277	19,091	(2,001)	90,001

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	Original 5-year Budget	5 Year Cumulative Budget	Year 1 Actuals	Year 2 Actuals	Year 3 Actuals	Year 4 Actuals	Year 4 Funds Remaining	Proposed Year 5 Budget
1.7 SEARCH BROCHURE								
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	-	1,090	1,090	-	-	-	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	4,652	4,652	-	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	-	5,741	5,741	-	-	-	-	-
Indirect Costs	-	2,384	2,384	-	-	-	-	-
Total direct and indirect costs	-	8,126	8,126	-	-	-	-	-

1.8 ARCTIC DATA SURVEY

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	-	235	-	-	235	-	9,072	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	7,250	-	-	1,100	6,150	(6,150)	-
Total direct costs	-	7,485	-	-	1,335	6,150	2,922	-
Indirect Costs	-	2,836	-	-	499	2,337	1,564	-
Total direct and indirect costs	-	10,322	-	-	1,835	8,487	4,486	-

2 NSF Arctic Sciences Section Coordination**2.1 ARCTIC SECTION SCIENCE MATERIALS**

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	13,282	14,901	6,799	1,597	210	-	4,536	6,296
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	11,500	6,622	241	1,208	874	1,333	2,167	2,967
Total direct costs	24,782	21,523	7,040	2,805	1,083	1,333	6,703	9,263
Indirect Costs	10,433	8,511	2,947	1,110	427	506	2,949	3,520
Total direct and indirect costs	35,215	30,034	9,987	3,915	1,510	1,839	9,653	12,783

2.2 ARCSS PROGRAM COORDINATION**2.2.1 ARCSS COORDINATION**

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	60,200	297,639	9,127	23,970	41,862	91,541	132,761	131,139
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	28,124	70,119	4,244	12,718	24,364	18,847	10,439	9,945
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	119,250	242,486	10,677	29,379	56,955	72,074	114,126	73,400
Other Direct Costs	18,096	529,971	6,226	51,816	116,507	129,223	74,360	226,200
Total direct costs	225,670	1,140,215	30,274	117,883	239,688	311,686	331,686	440,684
Indirect Costs	95,007	297,311	11,220	30,333	59,306	91,007	144,873	105,444
Total direct and indirect costs	320,677	1,437,526	41,494	148,217	298,994	402,693	476,558	546,128

2.2.2 ARCSS ALL-HANDS WORKSHOP

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	62,023	72,073	46,331	23,683	2,059	-	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	6,308	16,887	17,182	(294)	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	47,425	90,513	89,230	1,284	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	31,350	126,025	107,083	17,775	1,167	-	-	-
Total direct costs	147,106	305,498	259,825	42,447	3,226	-	-	-
Indirect Costs	61,932	111,189	95,062	15,015	1,112	-	-	-
Total direct and indirect costs	209,037	416,688	354,887	57,462	4,338	-	-	-

2.2.3 HARC SMO

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	31,957	47,167	20,151	6,780	20,236	-	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	14,268	6,643	1,249	953	4,441	0	(0)	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	39,807	29,846	1,686	3,891	24,269	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	65,948	81,687	21,363	17,776	42,549	-	-	-
Total direct costs	151,980	165,344	44,449	29,400	91,495	0	(0)	-
Indirect Costs	63,984	60,732	17,120	10,416	33,249	(52)	52	-
Total direct and indirect costs	215,964	226,076	61,569	39,815	124,744	(52)	52	-

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	Original 5-year Budget	5 Year Cumulative Budget	Year 1 Actuals	Year 2 Actuals	Year 3 Actuals	Year 4 Actuals	Year 4 Funds Remaining	Proposed Year 5 Budget
2.2.4 ARCTIC HYDROLOGY REPORT								
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	9,775	16,279	16,279	-	-	-	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	1,768	1,997	1,997	-	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	11,543	18,276	18,276	-	-	-	-	-
Indirect Costs	4,859	7,477	7,477	-	-	-	-	-
Total direct and indirect costs	16,402	25,753	25,753	-	-	-	-	-

2.3 ASSP PROGRAM COORDINATION

2.3.1 ARCTIC SOCIAL SCIENCES WORKSHOP

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	15,822	25,425	6,166	4,001	6,600	4,338	(1,638)	4,320
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	3,154	6,308	46	3,241	3,021	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	31,100	5,198	-	-	4,435	362	(362)	400
Other Direct Costs	13,984	59,304	254	614	56,462	74	(74)	1,900
Total direct costs	64,060	96,235	6,466	7,856	70,519	4,775	(2,075)	6,620
Indirect Costs	26,969	17,213	2,716	2,711	7,485	1,786	(625)	2,516
Total direct and indirect costs	91,029	113,449	9,182	10,566	78,004	6,561	(2,700)	9,136

2.3.2 GREENLAND BOOK

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	6,043	1,326	1,326	-	-	-	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	13,500	10,937	10,937	-	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	19,543	12,263	12,263	-	-	-	-	-
Indirect Costs	8,228	5,172	5,172	-	-	-	-	-
Total direct and indirect costs	27,771	17,435	17,435	-	-	-	-	-

2.3.3 ARCTIC SOCIAL SCIENCES VOLUME

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	-	8,211	2,733	5,371	107	-	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	1,556	-	1,556	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	2,838	-	2,380	458	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	27,455	13,200	13,865	390	-	-	-
Total direct costs	-	40,059	15,933	23,171	954	-	-	-
Indirect Costs	-	14,541	5,798	8,414	329	-	-	-
Total direct and indirect costs	-	54,600	21,731	31,586	1,283	-	-	-

2.3.4 BERING SEA COMMUNITY PLANNING

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	-	22,626	-	-	2,997	2,025	10,877	17,604
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	527	-	-	537	(10)	10	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	30,933	-	-	11,796	217	13,783	18,920
Other Direct Costs	-	14,977	-	-	71	4,206	(783)	10,700
Total direct costs	-	69,062	-	-	15,401	6,437	23,888	47,224
Indirect Costs	-	26,120	-	-	5,757	2,418	10,622	17,945
Total direct and indirect costs	-	95,182	-	-	21,158	8,855	34,510	65,169

3 Arctic Science Education

3.1 ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION ACTIVITIES

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	13,776	15,471	8,181	7,290	(0)	-	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	16,070	739	739	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	19,110	548	-	548	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	26,488	2,088	1,927	161	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	75,444	18,846	10,847	7,999	(0)	-	-	-
Indirect Costs	31,762	7,206	4,325	2,853	27	-	-	-
Total direct and indirect costs	107,205	26,052	15,172	10,852	27	-	-	-

3.2 ARCTIC VISITING SPEAKERS PROGRAM

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	27,181	46,551	9,599	8,353	8,251	10,446	(1,388)	9,902
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	148,500	84,063	27,301	13,195	15,612	12,534	2,866	15,420
Other Direct Costs	-	690	230	123	201	136	(136)	-
Total direct costs	175,681	131,304	37,130	21,671	24,064	23,117	1,342	25,322
Indirect Costs	73,962	49,568	14,772	7,740	8,690	8,743	1,774	9,622
Total direct and indirect costs	249,643	180,872	51,902	29,411	32,754	31,860	3,116	34,945

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	Original 5-year Budget	5 Year Cumulative Budget	Year 1 Actuals	Year 2 Actuals	Year 3 Actuals	Year 4 Actuals	Year 4 Funds Remaining	Proposed Year 5 Budget
3.3 ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION REPORT								
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	-	9,849	7,691	2,158	-	-	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	13,070	-	13,070	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	-	22,919	7,691	15,228	-	-	-	-
Indirect Costs	-	9,442	3,147	6,295	-	-	-	-
Total direct and indirect costs	-	32,361	10,838	21,523	-	-	-	-

3.4 ARCTIC ALIVE								
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	-	18,053	-	-	18,053	-	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	4,774	-	-	4,774	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	3,762	-	-	3,762	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	1,407	-	-	1,407	-	-	-
Total direct costs	-	27,996	-	-	27,996	-	-	-
Indirect Costs	-	10,114	-	-	10,114	-	-	-
Total direct and indirect costs	-	38,110	-	-	38,110	-	-	-

3.5 TREC								
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	-	101,046	-	-	19,418	45,098	(10,262)	36,530
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	1,989	-	-	-	-	1,627	1,989
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	9,350	-	-	-	-	-	9,350
Other Direct Costs	-	58,828	-	-	16,872	13,806	543	28,150
Total direct costs	-	171,214	-	-	36,291	58,905	(8,092)	76,019
Indirect Costs	-	64,629	-	-	13,565	22,176	(327)	28,887
Total direct and indirect costs	-	235,843	-	-	49,856	81,081	(8,419)	104,906

4 Information and Outreach

4.1 WITNESS THE ARCTIC NEWSLETTERS								
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	93,344	179,569	22,734	34,201	21,812	45,795	3,930	55,027
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	794	794	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	8,035	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	201,500	187,937	30,414	50,776	24,728	31,718	18,582	50,300
Total direct costs	302,879	368,300	53,943	84,978	46,540	77,513	22,512	105,327
Indirect Costs	127,512	137,655	20,799	30,120	17,369	29,342	13,668	40,024
Total direct and indirect costs	430,391	505,956	74,742	115,098	63,909	106,855	36,180	145,352

4.2 INTERNET RESOURCES								
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	372,565	439,219	52,897	47,674	74,125	110,240	(22,328)	154,283
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	21,890	1,740	1,330	7,029	5,791	(5,791)	6,000
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	49,388	14,102	5,933	8,154	8,799	(8,799)	12,400
Total direct costs	372,565	510,497	68,740	54,936	89,307	124,830	(36,918)	172,683
Indirect Costs	156,850	191,672	27,186	19,406	32,370	47,091	(9,288)	65,620
Total direct and indirect costs	529,414	702,169	95,926	74,342	121,678	171,921	(46,207)	238,303

4.3 ARCTIC INFO LISTSERVER								
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	98,790	72,726	12,430	10,446	20,013	19,244	736	10,595
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	4,593	78	1,840	-	2,675	(2,675)	-
Total direct costs	98,790	77,319	12,508	12,286	20,013	21,919	(1,939)	10,595
Indirect Costs	41,591	28,789	4,915	4,377	7,214	8,256	335	4,026
Total direct and indirect costs	140,381	106,108	17,423	16,663	27,226	30,175	(1,604)	14,621

4.4 DIRECTORY OF ARCTIC RESEARCHERS								
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	30,270	33,418	7,899	5,228	7,769	5,771	4,759	6,750
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	8,035	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	1,000	19,338	188	12,200	1,550	2,900	(400)	2,500
Total direct costs	39,305	52,756	8,087	17,428	9,319	8,671	4,359	9,250
Indirect Costs	16,548	19,577	3,236	6,292	3,324	3,210	2,392	3,515
Total direct and indirect costs	55,853	72,333	11,323	23,720	12,643	11,882	6,751	12,765

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	<u>Original 5-year Budget</u>	<u>5 Year Cumulative Budget</u>	<u>Year 1 Actuals</u>	<u>Year 2 Actuals</u>	<u>Year 3 Actuals</u>	<u>Year 4 Actuals</u>	<u>Year 4 Funds Remaining</u>	<u>Proposed Year 5 Budget</u>
4.5 INTERNET GRAPHICS ARCHIVE								
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	33,750	70,309	-	6,966	399	14,562	7,679	48,381
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	2,500	-	-	-	-	-	2,500
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	30,000	13,961	-	6,768	25	2,168	2,832	5,000
Total direct costs	63,750	86,770	-	13,734	424	16,730	10,511	55,881
Indirect Costs	26,839	32,586	-	4,847	147	6,357	5,356	21,235
Total direct and indirect costs	90,588	119,356	-	18,581	572	23,087	15,868	77,116

4.6 ARCTIC COMMUNITY OUTREACH

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	60,110	97,089	13,743	13,784	10,341	30,283	(18,808)	28,937
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	32,140	20,761	1,417	-	4,760	4,584	1,924	10,000
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	41,550	89,909	2,356	9,112	24,665	23,776	(9,726)	30,000
Other Direct Costs	75,090	136,782	29,356	30,905	10,713	29,787	(13,767)	36,020
Total direct costs	208,890	344,541	46,871	53,802	50,480	88,431	(40,378)	104,957
Indirect Costs	87,943	129,250	18,972	19,391	17,708	33,295	(12,632)	39,884
Total direct and indirect costs	296,833	473,791	65,843	73,193	68,188	121,726	(53,010)	144,841

4.7 PUBLICATION: THE ARCTIC

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	-	26,051	344	55	-	83	31,588	25,569
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	22,275	275	-	-	-	22,000	22,000
Total direct costs	-	48,326	619	55	-	83	53,588	47,569
Indirect Costs	-	18,367	239	20	-	32	23,047	18,076
Total direct and indirect costs	-	66,692	858	74	-	115	76,634	65,645

4.8 ENDANGERED SPECIES BULLETIN

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	-	2,617	2,150	468	-	-	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	-	2,617	2,150	468	-	-	-	-
Indirect Costs	-	952	782	170	-	-	-	-
Total direct and indirect costs	-	3,569	2,932	638	-	-	-	-

5 Core Support

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	990,334	874,522	157,403	145,307	171,239	186,028	21,294	214,545
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	86,808	70,746	11,770	11,046	17,437	12,321	5,576	18,172
Travel (foreign)	12,054	2,478	-	-	-	-	2,441	2,478
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	337,800	547,274	93,425	113,072	133,700	136,231	(42,386)	70,845
Total direct costs	1,426,996	1,495,019	262,598	269,426	322,376	334,580	(13,074)	306,040
Indirect Costs	600,765	556,741	103,275	95,633	115,629	125,909	12,338	116,295
Total direct and indirect costs	2,027,761	2,051,760	365,873	365,059	438,005	460,489	(736)	422,335

TOTAL PROGRAMS

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	2,491,867	3,300,535	495,519	453,064	666,342	663,747	235,066	1,021,863
Permanent Equipment	250	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	317,159	368,439	60,039	58,308	94,814	52,138	25,958	103,140
Travel (foreign)	12,054	2,478	-	-	-	-	2,441	2,478
Participant Support Costs	724,447	824,707	141,933	81,620	212,208	109,944	119,706	279,002
Other Direct Costs	999,542	2,367,172	364,955	374,430	675,280	384,824	88,396	567,682
Total direct costs	4,545,319	6,863,332	1,062,446	967,422	1,648,645	1,210,653	471,566	1,974,165
Indirect Costs	1,913,474	2,411,559	411,931	332,634	551,967	429,710	252,875	685,317
Total direct and indirect costs	6,458,793	9,274,891	1,474,377	1,300,056	2,200,612	1,640,364	724,441	2,659,482

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Form 1030 Category		Original 5 Year Budget	5 Year Cumulative Budget	Year 1 Actuals	Year 2 Actuals	Year 3 Actuals	Year 4 Actuals	Year 4 Funds Remaining	Proposed Year 5 Budget
Salaries									
President	A1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Executive director	A2	384,228	350,304	67,420	57,768	63,491	66,154	19,958	95,472
Other professionals	B2	1,290,167	1,809,139	257,366	242,803	364,762	363,887	133,728	580,321
Student	B3	-	67,304	8,411	11,243	19,755	13,431	(13,431)	14,465
Clerical	B5	213,383	236,635	39,702	28,636	50,523	50,640	31,420	67,134
Total salaries		1,887,778	2,463,381	372,898	340,450	498,530	494,112	171,675	757,392
Fringe Benefits									
Total salaries and fringe benefits	C	604,089	837,154	122,621	112,614	167,812	169,635	63,391	264,471
		2,491,867	3,300,535	495,519	453,064	666,342	663,747	235,066	1,021,863
Permanent Equipment									
	D	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)									
Travel (domestic)	E1	317,159	368,439	60,039	58,308	94,814	52,138	25,958	103,140
Travel (foreign)									
Travel (foreign)	E2	12,054	2,478	-	-	-	-	2,441	2,478
Participant Support Costs									
Stipends	F1	72,000	21,500	14,800	8,588	(4,938)	1,450	150	1,600
Travel	F2	418,360	401,506	54,779	39,726	101,431	50,340	55,552	155,230
Subsistence	F3	234,087	401,701	72,354	33,307	115,715	58,153	64,005	122,172
Total participant costs		724,447	824,707	141,933	81,620	212,208	109,944	119,706	279,002
Other Direct Costs									
Materials and supplies	G1	227,070	314,208	80,640	55,259	66,565	37,644	34,536	74,100
Publication cost/ docum/dissem	G2	443,272	431,381	63,719	95,442	93,239	57,674	89,187	121,307
Consultant services	G3	156,100	599,587	111,585	142,908	143,043	137,650	(65,850)	64,400
Computer services	G4	2,500	53,919	1,815	11,436	1,018	22,400	(21,900)	17,250
Subcontracts	G5	-	392,926	-	30,627	121,698	69,902	24,912	170,700
Other	G6	170,600	575,150	107,196	38,759	249,716	59,555	27,511	119,925
Total other direct costs		999,542	2,367,172	364,955	374,430	675,280	384,824	88,396	567,682
Total direct costs	H	4,545,069	6,863,332	1,062,446	967,422	1,648,645	1,210,653	471,566	1,974,165
Indirect									
	I	1,913,474	2,411,559	411,931	332,634	551,967	429,710	252,875	685,317
Total	J	6,458,543	9,274,891	1,474,377	1,300,056	2,200,612	1,640,364	724,441	2,659,482

**SUMMARY
PROPOSAL BUDGET**

YEAR 5 OF 5

4/1/05 to 3/31/06

REVISED FOR NSF USE ONLY

ORGANIZATION Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.			PROPOSAL NO.: 0101279		DURATION (MONTHS) Proposed Granted	
PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR/PROJECT DIRECTOR Wendy K. Warnick			AWARD NO.			
A. SENIOR PERSONNEL: PI/PD, Co-PI's, Faculty and other Senior Associates (List each separately with title; A.7 show number in brackets)			NSF Funded Person-mos.		Funds Requested By Proposer	Funds Granted By NSF (If Different)
1. Wendy K. Warnick , Executive Director			CAL	ACAD	SUMR	
			10.8			95,472
2.						
3.						
4.						
5.						
6.() OTHERS (LIST INDIVIDUALLY ON BUDGET EXPLANATION PAGE)						
7. (1) TOTAL SENIOR PERSONNEL (1-5)						95,472
B. OTHER PERSONNEL (SHOW NUMBERS IN BRACKETS)						
1.() POST DOCTORAL ASSOCIATES						
2.(18) OTHER PROFESSIONALS (TECHNICIAN, PROGRAMMER, ETC.)						580,321
3.() GRADUATE STUDENTS						
4.(1) UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS						14,465
5.(2) SECRETARIAL-CLERICAL						67,134
6.() OTHER						
TOTAL SALARIES AND WAGES (A+B)						757,392
C. FRINGE BENEFITS (IF CHARGED AS DIRECT COSTS)						264,471
TOTAL SALARIES, WAGES, AND FRINGE BENEFITS (A+B+C)						1,021,863
D. PERMANENT EQUIPMENT (LIST ITEM AND DOLLAR AMOUNT FOR EACH ITEM EXCEEDING \$1,000.)						
TOTAL PERMANENT EQUIPMENT						
E. TRAVEL						
1. DOMESTIC (INCL. CANADA AND U.S. POSSESSIONS)			103,140			
2. FOREIGN			2,478			
F. PARTICIPANT SUPPORT COSTS						
1. STIPENDS \$ 1,600						
2. TRAVEL 155,230						
3. SUBSISTENCE 122,172						
4. OTHER						
110) TOTAL PARTICIPANT COSTS			279,002			
G. OTHER DIRECT COSTS						
1. MATERIALS AND SUPPLIES			74,100			
2. PUBLICATION COSTS/DOCUMENTATION/DISSEMINATION			121,307			
3. CONSULTANT SERVICES			64,400			
4. COMPUTER (ADPE) SERVICES			17,250			
5. SUBCONTRACTS			170,700			
6. OTHER			119,925			
TOTAL OTHER DIRECT COSTS			567,682			
H. TOTAL DIRECT COSTS (A THROUGH G)			1,974,165			
I. INDIRECT COSTS (SPECIFY RATE AND BASE) 38% on (H) - (D) - (G5)						
TOTAL INDIRECT COSTS			685,317			
J. TOTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT COSTS (H+I)			2,659,482			
K. RESIDUAL FUNDS (IF FOR FURTHER SUPPORT OF CURRENT PROJECTS SEE GPM 252 AND 253)			724,441			
L. AMOUNT OF THIS REQUEST (J) OR (J MINUS K)			1,935,041			
M. COST SHARING: PROPOSED LEVEL \$			AGREED LEVEL IF DIFFERENT \$			
PI/PD TYPED NAME & SIGNATURE *					FOR NSF USE ONLY	
Wendy K. Warnick			17 Jun 05		INDIRECT COST RATE VERIFICATION	
INST. REP. TYPED NAME & SIGNATURE			Date Checked	Date of Rate Sheet	Initials-DGC	
Wendy K. Warnick			17 Jun 05			